

D1.2

Initial System and Signal Processing Design

WP1

System Analysis and Design

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Abstract

This deliverable provides an initial analysis, from a signal processing viewpoint, of the different solutions proposed to support the multiple 6G functionalities. Therefore, a system study has been performed to derive the requirements to meet the communication, sensing and synchronization functionalities defined in D1.1. Different techniques (e.g. algorithms, system architecture) are described and validated by simulation.

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6G Communication systems, Distributed MIMO (D-MIMO), Full Duplex, Beamforming, Integrated Communication and Sensing, Radar, Phased Arrays, Frequency synchronization, Time Synchronization, UTC time, Time Modulated Array, Frequency Modulated Array, OFDM, Self-Interference Cancellation, Simulation

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DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Acronyms and definitions

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
A/D	Analog-to-Digital
ACLR	Adjacent Channel Leakage Ratio
ACS	Adjacent Channel Selectivity
ADC	Analog-to-Digital Converter
ANT	Antenna array
AP	Access Point or Radio Unit (RU) that serves the UEs (the term RU and AP are used interchangeably in this report)
BRAN	Block oriented Radio Access Network
CFO	Common Frequency Offset
CIR	Channel Impulse Response
CLI	Cross Link Interference
COM	Communications
CPE	Common Phase Error
DoA	Description of Action
D-MIMO	Distributed MIMO
FIR	Finite Impulse Response
FMA	Frequency Modulated Array
FuDu	Full Duplex: simultaneous communication in 2 directions
FR3	Frequency Range 3
HF	High Frequency
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communication
IF	Intermediate Frequency
IFFT	Inverse Fast Fourier Transform
LO	Local Oscillator
LoS	Line of Sight
MPC	Multi Path Component
OAS	Over the Air Synchronization
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplex
OVFS	Orthogonal variable spreading factor

PLL	Phase Locked Loop
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
QAM	Quadrature Amplitude Modulation
RF	Radio Frequency
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces
Rx	Receiver
RU	Radio Unit that serves as access point to the 6G network
SENS	Sensing the environment (e.g. radar-like) as well as environmental conditions (e.g. Physical variable sensing like temperature, humidity...)
SI	Self Interference
SIC	Self Interference Cancellation
SYNC	Synchronization, can be in frequency, phase and time.
TDEV	Time deviation: figure of merit for time drift
Tx	Transmitter
TRx	(Combined) Transmitter-Receiver
UE	User Equipment
SYNC	Synchronization, usually in either frequency, phase or time
TD	Time Division
TDD	Time Division Duplex
TMA	Time Modulated Array
TSN	Time Sensitive Network
Tx	Transmitter
UE	User Equipment
UTC	Universal Time Coordinated
WP	Work Package
WRC27	2027 World Radiocommunication Conference
XO	Crystal Oscillator
ZF	Zero Forcing

1. Executive summary

This report describes the outcome of initial explorative research on the 6G-REFERENCE target system with focus on signal processing aspects.

6G-REFERENCE envisions dense cell-free distributed Radio Unit deployments offering cm-wave integrated communications and sensing capabilities. Leveraging distributed MIMO will allow for reduced interference, enhanced coverage and reliability, higher data rates and improved power efficiency. However, fiber access cannot be taken for granted if we target very dense deployment, e.g. 10-30 m AP-spacing. Hence, fast high-capacity wireless data communication and over the air wireless synchronization (SYNC) are key challenges. Moreover, 6G is pushed towards sustainable solutions, while also providing disruptive capabilities like the internet of sense. Realizing Integrated Sensing And Communication (ISAC) functionality in practical Integrated Circuit (IC) and antenna hardware with low complexity, cost, and power consumption is a key objective.

More specifically, project 6G-REFERENCE targets a reference design for IC-hardware for an antenna with radio transceiver front-end operating in the 14.8-15.3GHz band, that is under discussion as future 6G-band [WRC-23 Resolution 256 (2023)].

6G-REFERENCE simultaneously aims to support 3 main functionalities:

- COM: wireless communication between a cluster of Access Points (APs) and User Equipment (UE), where only one of the access points has high-capacity fiber-internet access. Hence high data rate and low latency is key for wireless data distribution between APs, leading to the choice to target in-band full duplex for AP-AP links, while more traditional TDD will still be targeted for the AP-UE links. Please note that in this report the terms AP and RU (Radio Unit) are interchangeable.
- SENS: sensing functionality to monitor the environment with radar-like functionality (ISAC), positioning of UEs, as well as physical parameter sensing.
- SYNC: synchronization in frequency and time of APs and UEs, that have only a wireless link to rely on (no cable/fiber internet access, except for one node).

In deliverable D1.1 you can find initial system specifications for the COM, SENS and SYNC functionality. This report describes system design considerations clarifying the supported functionalities and especially choices for the signal processing. Below find the main features of the system and related signal processing aspects.

- *Compact Antenna Array 8x4*: A relatively small reconfigurable 8x4 antenna array is targeted, where the number and positions of Tx and Rx elements can be flexibly

reconfigured. This small array size is chosen as it suffices the link budget for the target AP-deployment scenarios with about 25m distance between APs operating in the 15GHz band, while still providing some spatial filtering by beamforming.

- *Reconfigurable in-band full duplex Tx/Rx COM*: To support fast low latency data communication between APs, in-band full duplex is explored. For cost and compactness reasons reconfigurable transceiver hardware is targeted supporting full duplex, but also classic TD half-duplex and radar (see below).
- *Spatial self-interference cancellation*: Mutual antenna coupling in a compact low cost antenna array is found to be a key challenge for realizing sufficient SI-rejection. We propose to explore spatial self-interference cancellation techniques leveraging adaptive beamforming to bring this SI-level down.
- *Time Modulated Array (TMA)*: TMA exploit beamforming hardware in a time-multiplexed way to simultaneously support multiple beams with the same hardware. We propose to not only exploit this for Rx but also for Tx. Moreover, we explore time-domain isolation techniques to enable a full duplex sensing mode.
- *COM-centric Integrated Sensing And Communication (ISAC)*: we aim for radio hardware primarily designed for COM-functionality, and choose radar waveforms fitting to the COM-hardware capabilities. This choice is made as high-capacity COM-functionality is considered the primary driver for the two considered use scenarios: 1) an urban square with dense amount of users and 2) a factory hall scenario with high UE-density and both fixed and mobile equipment.
- *OFDM-radar waveform*: We aim for a communication centric sensing approach, where we re-use the OFDM COM-hardware. An adapted OFDM radar waveform design is proposed with lowered peak-to-average Ratio and the use of Pi/K phase modulation to reduce the effect of I/Q and nonlinearity impairments.
- *SYNC-TIME*: Initial synchronization in time based on known pseudo-random sequences is targeted. The performance limits of traditional correlator-based solutions with fixed threshold level have been explored and a new adaptive threshold based technique is proposed.
- *SYNC in FREQUENCY and PHASE*: wireless over-the-air synchronization (OAS) in frequency and phase is targeted, which is ultimately limited by different noise sources. System modelling and analysis show that especially long-term stability of the Crystal Oscillator (XO) reference will be a main bottleneck defining the minimum required synchronization-update frequency, while white noise of the radio channel leads to a minimum required integration time to average out noise.
- *SYNC-TIMESTAMPING*: time-stamping with better accuracy than 100nsec is targeted. This seems quite feasible hardware wise, but the impact of multi-path

effects and hardware imperfections on ultimate feasible resolution needs further study.

2. Introduction

The goal of this deliverable is to provide a system level study of the different solutions proposed to meet the requirements defined in D1.1 for the COM, SENS and SYNC functionalities. In D1.1 you can also find motivations for high system level choices and the focus on dense cell free network deployments in urban square and factory user scenarios. The current report provides the main outcomes of initial system studies, providing design choice motivations and some mathematical background for the performance of different proposed solutions. Some information on the proposed signal processing can also be found in this report, and some system simulation results based on macro-models of the hardware and signal processing algorithms. For hardware design details we refer to D2.1 (Antenna Design), D2.3 (Physical Sensing), D3.1 (IC Design) and D4.1 (Demonstrator Plans for Individual Hardware Enablers).

This report is structured as follows.

Chapter 3 discusses the main top-level applications of the 6G-REFERENCE hardware. It translates the scenario requirements from D1.1 into system specifications for COM, SENS and SYNC functionalities.

Chapter 4 starts with channel simulations for a factory hall environment. This indoor environment was chosen as this user scenario lacks GPS access, making sensing and positioning using 6G-REFERENCE hardware even more valuable than in an urban square scenario. Also, high precision synchronization with accurate time stamping and low latency communication exploiting full duplex are clearly relevant for factory hall scenarios (“Time Sensitive Networks”). Hence system simulations focus on that.

Chapter 4 also describes simulation chains which have been developed to support RF transceiver chip design, taking into account self-interference aspects in the antenna array.

Chapter 5 discusses signal processing aspects for the COM, SENS and SYNC applications, and explores some potential feasibility limitations related to the requirements defined in chapter 3.

Finally, chapter 6 dives into full duplex self-interference techniques that we selected and explored in the first phase of the 6G-REFERENCE project. Given the phased array context with rather strong coupling between antenna elements in the array, the main focus is on spatial SIC techniques relying on various forms of beamforming.

Chapter 7 finishes with conclusions.

3. Main System Applications

3.1. Antenna Model

Based on the system specifications in D1.1, different antenna options were explored in WP2. For the access point (AP) design considerations are collected in D2.1. Here we briefly describe one of the configurations, which is used as a baseline for the analysis carried out in the rest of the document.

Figure 3.1 depicts a top view of the considered antenna array. It consists of 8×4 dual-polarized microstrip patch elements, resulting in a total of 64 antenna ports, 32 for each polarization. The separation between the centre of the elements is 10 mm corresponding to a half-wavelength at an operating central frequency of 15 GHz. The size of the patches is $5.75 \times 5.75 \text{ mm}^2$. They are placed on a grounded dielectric slab with a thickness of 0.76 mm and an $\epsilon_r = 2.55$. They are fed through coaxial pins located in the two main axes to excite the two orthogonal polarizations. The simulated gain and return loss at 15 GHz are better than 4 dB and 10 dB, respectively.

We group antennas in a Tx and Rx array, where each antenna element has a horizontal and vertical polarization port. A digital beamforming architecture is considered, in which each antenna port can be connected either to a Tx or an Rx RF-chain through an RF-switch. In this way the number of simultaneously active Tx and Rx ports can be configured flexibly accordingly to different requirements for communication, sensing and synchronization. For communications, a baseline configuration consists of splitting the array on two arrays of $4 \times 4 \times 2$ antenna ports and using one for Tx and the other for Rx. Under this framework, Figure 3.2 shows the coupling of the central element marked in black in Figure 3.1, with all the ports in the Rx subarray. The largest couplings are observed for the element marked in white and more specifically, for the vertical polarization to vertical polarization ports. Note that those couplings are the main source of the self-interference experienced in full duplex communications.

Figure 3.1 Top view on the baseline antenna array for 6G-REFERENCE APs. A configuration for communications is shown with half the array for Tx (red square) and half for Rx (green square). The black square identifies the central element for which the couplings are plot in Figure 3.2, while the white square identifies the element with the highest coupling levels.

Figure 3.2 Couplings for a central element marked in black in Figure 3.1. Line and dashed-line curves correspond to the horizontal and vertical port, respectively.

3.2. Communication

In 6G-REFERENCE, we explore the feasibility of a 15GHz antenna and IC hardware design compatible with cell-free user-centric Distributed MIMO and ISAC. It leverages a dense network of approximately 25m spaced wireless AP-nodes and explores the feasibility in-band full duplex between these nodes, as high-performance alternative for well established broadly used TD-techniques. A small cluster of cooperating APs serves each UE (Figure 3.3). Being connected to nearby APs can improve coverage (avoid cell-

boundary issues), guarantee quality of service, support ultra-high reliability, support low latency and reduce power consumption due to the short-distance links with a high probability of line-of-sight connection (Galappaththigeet al. 2024).

Figure 3.3 Simplified example of a distributed MIMO system with only one cabled 6G-network node providing data and an accurate time and frequency reference. APs cooperate to serve UEs, provide ISAC functionality and establish Over-the-Air Synchronization (OAS). Full-Duplex AP-AP links support Sync signals (green) and data distribution/gathering (blue arrows)

Our 6G-REFERENCE system will use OFDM and can use established TDD techniques for the AP-AP and AP-UE link. However, we also aim for full duplex to realize high-capacity data-distribution/gathering, fast synchronization and low latency. Some of the guiding principles of the design of the 6G-REFERENCE system are:

- Low-power full duplex AP-AP links to minimize Cross Link Interference (CLI), which is a key bottleneck for in-band full duplex in the context of cellular macro base-stations as discussed in [Giupponi, 2023].
- Wireless APs for easy deployment without requiring a fiber/cabled internet.
- Exploiting beamforming to realize sufficient isolation between different AP-AP links to allow for simultaneous operation of multiple AP-AP links.
- Keep signal-to-noise ratio variations across the coverage area small due to small AP-AP distance of 25m. As the APs are placed along the ceiling or at a few meters height, the ratio between the longest and shortest communication distance is in the order of 1:10, which is one or 2 orders of magnitude lower than for traditional cell-based systems. This reduces the near-far power-ratio significantly and makes power-control much less needed, which is relaxes the required dynamic range of the Rx hardware and ADCs. Moreover, beamforming can help to reduce CLI.

- Modular flexibly reconfigurable hardware solutions that can be re-used for different applications (ISAC), while both support full duplex and more established time domain duplexing techniques.
- Aim for low complexity compact hardware solutions with low power consumption: search for simple but effective hardware solutions.

We will now discuss the link budget of the different radio-links in the system, namely the TD AP-AP link, the TD AP-UE link and the Full Duplex AP-AP link. The aim is to show that for relatively limited hardware complexity sufficient link budget performance is likely feasible. Antenna and IC hardware design details can be found in other deliverables, mentioned in the introduction chapter 2.

3.2.1. TDD AP-AP link budget

In the considered D-MIMO grid, to achieve the fronthaul segment capacity greater than number of co-scheduled UEs (i.e. 4 UEs in the assumed use case), the inter-RU link budget is derived with 400MHz channel bandwidth, 256-QAM modulation scheme and considering a LoS propagation condition. Figure 3.4 reiterates the fronthaul link budget calculation from the D1.1 report, highlighting the link margin suffices with 16 elements in the antenna array for each transmit and receive aperture.

	Inter-RU link @15GHz Wideband 400MHz
Transmitter	
P1dB at PA output (dBm)	15
Output power back off (dB)	9
Mean power at PA output (dBm)	6
Antenna interconnection loss (dB)	3
Mean Power at antenna input (dBm)	3
Number of PAs	16
Emitted mean power (dBm)	15
Antenna gain patch antenna element (dB)	3
Number of TX antennas el.=#PAs	16
Transmit array efficiency (%)	100
Antenna gain (dB)	15
EIRP (dBm)	30
EIRP max (dBm)	39
Path loss (dB)	-84.0
Receiver	
Number of RX antennas el.	16
Total Rx antenna gain (dBi)	15
LNA-antenna interconnection loss (dB)	3
Power at FEM input (dBm)=EIRP+Path_loss+Grx-LrxAn	-42
Single antenna Rx power level	-54
Noise figure (dB)	6
Target SNR for 256 QAM (dB)	30
Target Sensitivity	-65
Link margin [dB]	23

Figure 3.4. Fronthaul link budget with 16 Tx and 16 Rx array elements

3.2.2. TDD AP-UE link budget

The access link budget is recalculated in Figure 3.5 with respect to D1.1 [6G-REFERENCE D1.1, 2024)], while including a shadow fading loss of 6dB. The extent of SNR improvement possible (assuming ideal fronthaul) with coherent transmission from multiple-RUs in the D-MIMO network will be evaluated during this project, based on the performance of hardware enablers e.g. an over-the-air synchronizing (OAS) module.

	Downlink (RU -> UE) @15GHz			Uplink (UE -> RU) @15GHz		
	Wideband 400MHz	Medium 100MHz	Narrow 50MHz	Wideband 400MHz	Medium 100MHz	Narrow 50MHz
Transmitter						
P1dB at PA output (dBm)	15	15	15	20	20	20
Output power back off (dB)	7	7	7	7	7	7
Mean power at PA output (dBm)	8	8	8	13	13	13
Antenna interconnection loss (dB)	3	3	3	3	3	3
Mean Power at antenna input (dBm)	5	5	5	10	10	10
Number of PAs	16	16	16	1	1	1
Emitted mean power (dBm)	17	17	17	10	10	10
Antenna gain patch antenna element (dB)	3	3	3	3	3	3
Number of TX antennas el.=#PAs	16	16	16	1	1	1
Transmit array efficiency (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100
Antenna gain (dB)	15	15	15	3	3	3
EIRP (dBm)	32	32	32	13	13	13
EIRP max (dBm)	39	39	39	20	20	20
Path loss (dB) (including fading margin = 6dB)	-90.0	-90.0	-90.0	-90.0	-90.0	-90.0
Receiver						
Number of RX antennas el.	1	1	1	16	16	16
Total Rx antenna gain (dBi)	3	3	3	15	15	15
LNA-antenna interconnection loss (dB)	3	3	3	3	3	3
Power at FEM input (dBm)=EIRP+Path_loss+Grx-LrxAn	-58	-58	-58	-65	-65	-65
Single antenna Rx power level	-58	-58	-58	-77	-77	-77
Noise figure (dB)	7	7	7	6	6	6
Target SNR for 64 QAM (dB)	20	20	20	25	25	25
Target Sensitivity	-62	-68	-71	-69	-75	-78
Link margin [dB]	4	10	13	4	10	13

Figure 3.5. Access link budget with 16 Tx/Rx array

With respect to adjacent channel coexistence , minimum ACLR and ACS of 30dB is targeted for the RU, as per 3GPP-38.922 [3GPP, 2025a].

3.2.3. Full duplex AP-AP link budget

It is well-known that for in-band full duplex, the link budget is heavily limited by Self-Interference (SI) from Tx- to the co-located Rx that tries to receive a remote signal while the Tx is transmitting another signal Kolodziej, 2019][Nagulu,2024][Smida,2024]. We have modelled several SI-induced impairments to assess the feasibility of a full-duplex AP-AP link in the 15GHz band. We built on the model proposed in [Debaillie,2014], but adapted it to model phased array multi-antenna coupling effects in antenna arrays. To model coupling, the s-parameter model for the baseline array discussed in section 3.1 was used. Based on link-budget calculations for the AP-UE and AP-AP TDD links in the previous sections, we concluded that a 16-element Tx-array and Rx-array, so 32 elements in total, would be sufficient to satisfy TD-link budget requirements. We will now examine whether this also satisfies the link-budget for a full duplex AP-AP link.

Figure 3.6 Example of the use of the 8x4 Antenna Array with columns c1-c8 and rows r1-r4 of dual-polarized (H/V) patch-antennas connected in groups of 4 to reconfigurable Transceiver ICs supporting a Transmit mode (Tx), Receive mode (Rx) and passive load mode (load).

Antenna array modeling and initial SI-simulations

The proposed 8x4 antenna array is once again shown in Figure 3.6, but now with colouring related to the patch antenna role. To avoid compromising TDD data capacity, both the vertical and horizontal polarization are used independently. The array is modular and per cluster of 4 dual polarized antenna patches an 8-channel Tx-Rx IC is added (small black boxes in Figure 3.6) to support 3 modes of operation: 1) Transmit (Tx, red), 2) Receive (Rx, green) and 3) load (50ohm termination). This latter mode is added for realizing antenna separation while aiming for dissipating SI-power. Note that this array configuration is flexibly reconfigurable, as each patch antenna can be Tx, Rx and load, as will be detailed in later chapters. This is not only useful for communication, but also for sensing and synchronization as will be discussed in later sections.

To assess SI-power, antenna EM-simulations were performed and stored in the form of a 64-port s-parameter model, modelling mutual coupling between elements. We then explored several Tx/Rx configurations and studied how SI contributions from multiple transmit antenna patches add up at different Rx patches.

This resulted in the following initial conclusions:

- 1) Adding load-elements between the Tx and Rx reduces SI to the Rx but parasitic propagation modes, like surface waves, still limit SI-isolation.
- 2) Using an even number of Tx-columns with $\lambda/2$ spacing tends to reduce SI-power in the Rx-direction orthogonal to the Tx-column. The reason is likely that for broadside drive, surface waves tend to cancel each other for path-length differences which are a multiple of $\lambda/2$. This leads us to a preference for double-column or double-row Tx-configurations, e.g. the one shown in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7 Antenna Isolation simulation results for an example 16-element Tx configuration and 8-element Rx-configuration demonstrating that azimuth beam-direction steering significantly degrades Rx-Self-Interference power levels (note that of broadside SI-power is <-33.5dBm but it seriously degrades to worst-case -22.1dBm for +60 degrees beam steering).

- 3) Beamforming is especially effective in increasing the EIRP in the Tx-beam which improves the link-budget by $20\log(n_{Tx})$ (assuming n_{Tx} equal PAs are used), while Rx-beamforming improves it by "only" $10\log(n_{Rx})$. Still, Rx-beamforming is highly wanted to implement Rx-directionality in order to realize some level of isolation between different simultaneously active AP-AP links. Rx-interference nulling or tapering can be leveraged to maximize such CLI.
- 4) We tend to see best isolation results at broadside, where surface waves nominally cancel each other to first order in the configuration of Figure 3.6. However, when steering the beam in azimuth, SI-level at the Rx element increase significantly from a worst-case -33.5dBm at 0 angle to -22.0dBm at +60 degrees steering angle (see Figure 3.7). This level of SI can potentially saturate traditional LNA-designs,

even for the scenarios with a limited 0dBm Tx-power per element. We will later propose “Spatial SIC” techniques that can reduce this Rx-input SI-power level.

Full duplex link budget model and parameters

We will now make an estimate of the full duplex link budget and key limitations that will likely limit performance. The modelling of full duplex impairments follows equations derived for a single Tx-Rx antenna pair [Debaillie,2014]. However, the analysis of Tx-EVM needs attention because it is different in a phased array context. This is because Tx-EVM from several transmitters can contribute to a single Rx-element. However, different Tx-elements will likely have different Tx-signals, e.g. due to beamforming. Hence the Tx-signal is different and Tx-EVM contributions due to PA-nonlinearity and DAC quantization noise are likely largely uncorrelated. It will then be difficult to combat Tx-EVM with RF-SIC techniques, commonly used in a low-GHz full duplex system. Potentially there is still some role for RF-SIC if the Rx is co-located with a Tx-element, or if a 50ohm load mode is used, while sensing Tx-EVM signals. This is not further considered here but may be explored further later. For now, no RF-SIC, so RF-SIC=0dB is assumed.

Several potential full duplex link budget limitations are modelled and educated guesses for parameter values were done. In the top 4 rows, you find the main assumptions for the calculations:

- An RF-frequency of 15GHz, BW=400MHz (widest bandwidth preference)
- Antenna isolation of 30dB (based on simulations in Figure 3.7)
- Spatial SIC rejection of 20dB (rather limited value, also considering analog phase shifter options that may be narrowband and limited by quantization)
- Number of Tx-elements $n_{Tx}=16$ (see Figure 3.6)
- AP-AP communication distance = 25m
- No RF-SIC (=0dB)
- EVM-density of -172dBV/Hz (discussed in more detail below)
- Number of Rx-elements $n_{Rx}=8$ (see Figure 3.6)
- Rx-NF = Rx Noise Figure = 6dB
- BB-SIC = Baseband Self-Interference Cancellation = 30dB
- Rx-IIP3 = Rx Input Referred Third-Order Intercept Point = 0dBm (good linearity)
- P_Tx element = Tx power per Tx-element = 0dBm
- GantPatch = antenna patch gain (6dB) – insertion loss (3dB) = 3dB
- Rx-CP1dB = Receiver 1dB Compression Point = -20dBm
- PA_OIP3 = PA Output Referred Third-Order Intercept Point = +25dBm

We aim for a total targeted SI reduction of 80dB, divided here in 30dB antenna isolation, 20dB Spatial SIC and 30dB Baseband-SIC. RF-SIC is set to 0dB, as it is not obvious how RF-SIC can be implemented in an array context with numerous Tx-Rx path contributions. Also, note that the Tx hardware may be in one IC, and the Rx in another IC, so that it is not obvious how to detect and subtract SI from the Rx-signal. Also note that not all SI reduction techniques apply equally to different SI-components. Hence, only the nominal SI benefits from the full 80dB SI-rejection, but Tx-EVM for instance does not benefit from digital BB-SIC as it is non-deterministic, e.g. due to DAC quantization noise.

In the excel spreadsheet shown in Figure 3.8, four potential limitations of the SNDR of the AP-AP link are estimated: limitations due to thermal noise (yellow), due to residual SI (dark orange/brown), due to Rx-EVM (green) and due to Tx-EVM (orange/red). Phase noise is not considered as the Rx- and Tx-clock tend to share a PLL and phase noise then is cancelled to first order [Broek,2015].

The top red-coloured fields calculate the Tx-EIRP, starting from 0dBm per Tx-element, adding 3dB patch-antenna gain, $10 \cdot \log(n_{Tx})=12\text{dB}$ to find Total Radiated Power (TRP) and finally EIRP in dBm (12dB Tx-antenna gain, 16 Tx-elements). After subtracting 84dB Path-loss (blue field, line-of-sight link of 25m distance with a path-loss coefficient 2), the Rx-power is found to be -54dBm/patch-antenna (light green including GantPatch=3dB). Now we assume the received wanted signal contributions are fully correlated and perfectly aligned by constructive beamforming. This gives then overall n_{Rx} power contributions as well as $10 \cdot \log(n_{Rx})$ antenna gain, i.e. in total $20 \cdot \log(n_{Rx})=18\text{dB}$. This results in -36dBm total Rx power used as S =Signal Power for all SNDR calculations.

In yellow fields you find the Rx-noise floor calculation, i.e. $-174\text{dBm/Hz} + 10\log(\text{BW})$. Here $10 \cdot \log(n_{Rx})=9\text{dB}$ is added, as the thermal noise of different Rx-antennas is uncorrelated. We find then an $\text{SNR}=37\text{dB}$ limited by the thermal noise floor. Ideally all other S -to- xx ratios should be higher than this SNR, but for 256-QAM 30dB SNR is sufficient, so a few contributions in total adding up to -30dB is likely also acceptable.

For the S -to-SI we see it benefits from antenna isolation (30dB), Spatial SIC (20dB) and BB-SIC (30dB), i.e. the full 80dB SI Reduction. This results in 35dB S -to-SI residue.

For the Rx-EVM calculation the dark-green field with white text start from -30dBm worst case Rx-SI per antenna element. Given a IIP3 of 0dBm, the IM3-floor caused by this is $2 \cdot (\text{IIP3} - P_{in}) = 2 \cdot (0 - -30)=60\text{dB}$ below the SI-power, i.e. -90dBm. Assuming uncorrelated Rx-EVM contributions for differential Rx-antennas, we find $10 \cdot \log(n_{Rx})=9\text{dB}$ more total Rx-EVM equal to -81dBm, resulting in 45dB S -Rx-EVM ratio. Note that improving IIP3 by 10dB makes this ratio 20dB better. However, compression can also be a problem, especially if a receiver with large gain is used.

Tx-EVM modelling deserves special attention, as it may easily become the bottleneck in a phased array full duplex system, unlike single-antenna full duplex systems with RF-SIC not only reduces SI but also Tx-EVM.

To model this, we used a very simple modelling approach: we raised the thermal noise temperature of all 50ohm Tx-element drivers to produce strong uncorrelated white noise at the Tx-EVM floor level. Based on experimental results obtained with cascode class-AB linear PAs [Broek, Klumperink et al. 2015], we estimate achievable OIP3=+25dBm. This results in an Tx-EVM of -50dB at 0dBm Tx-power, which for 400MHz channel bandwidth can be modelled as a 50ohm resistor with 1 million Kelvin noise temperature. We then simulate the equivalent noise voltage after Rx-beamforming (depends on the Rx-array configuration) and convert that to a Tx-EVM residual in the Rx. In the lowest row of Figure 3.8 (light orange field), where this calculation can be found, leading to a Tx-power to Tx-EVM ratio of 37dB.

Comparing all results we find a worst case SNDR of 35dB and summed power likely just good enough for -30dB EVM required for 256-QAM.

Summarizing, the 8x4 array seems large enough to support a full-duplex link budget. It will be challenging to achieve 80dB overall SIC, and it will likely be necessary to combine the limited Antenna Isolation with Spatial SIC, to achieve together e.g. 50dB and add another 30dB of Baseband SIC (using the digital Tx-signal directly for baseband cancellation after adding proper delay and/or amplitude/phase shifting in baseband).

ARRAY ANTENNA Full Duplex link budget estimates									
RF-frequency	15	n_Tx=	16	n_Rx	8			GantPatch	3
BW	400	distance	25	Rx-NF	6	RX-IIP3	0	RX-CP1dB	-20
Ant Isolation	30	RF-SIC	0	BB-SIC	30	P_Tx element	0	PA_OIP3	25
Spatial SIC	20	EVM-density	-172	dBV/Hz (SpectreRF simulation with Tnoise=1Mohm)					
>>>> Tx-EIRP calc.:>> +G_TxArray 27.0824 =EIRP[dBm]									
TRP(total rad) = 15.04119983 dBm -84 dB Path-Loss <= Desired link									
+GPatch= 3 dBm/patch -57 dBm <= desired Rx calc.									
P_Tx: 0 dBm/element +GPatch= -54 dBm/patch									
>>>> SNR calc.:>> Rx Noise=> -174dB/Hz + 10*log(BW)= -88 dbm/patch -36 dBm total Rx-power (opt. correlated BF)									
+NF: -82 dBm									
>>>> P_Tx - Ant Isolation -30 dBm +10*log(nRx) -73 dBm Noise power after beamforming									
-RF-SIC-Spatial-SIC: -50 dBm SI@Rx									
-BB-SIC: -80 dBm SI residue									
>>>> LNA-SI if Spatial SIC does NOT target LNA-SI (pessim) -30 dBm +10*LOG(nRx) -71 SNR - thermal 37 dB									
If "Spatial SIC" would NOT minimize LNA Pinput, P_IM3 = -90 dBm S-to-SI residue 35 dB									
+10*LOG(nRx)= -81 dBm S-RxEVM Ratio 45 dB									
>>>> Tx "EVM" density @Tnoise=1E6 K + 10*log10(BW): -73.0 dBm S-TxEVM estimate 37 dB									
									Worst SNDR: 35 dB

Figure 3.8 Example of a link budget estimate indicating that the Full-Duplex Link-Budget may be feasible. The header of the table lists the main assumptions (see text) and the bottom part shows how SNR limitations due to different artefacts are estimated for the following key Full Duplex SNR-limitations: 1) Thermal Noise; 2) Nominal Self-Interference; 3) Receiver EVM due to limited Rx-IIP3; 4) Transmitter EVM due to limited Tx-OIP3.

3.3. Sensing

The radar waveform must be designed to meet the requirements defined in D1.1. The proposed OFDM radar must be able to detect a 0dBsm target at 13m while the maximum unambiguous range is 25m and the range resolution is 0.5m. In order to achieve such detection capabilities, the proposed radar must provide a SNR of 15 dB for this target (see Figure 3.9).

Two radar waveforms are explored. The first one is an OFDM radar waveform in time-domain MIMO which has the advantage of being able to reuse the hardware used for communication (as OFDM is also used for wireless communication). The second one is Frequency Modulated Array (FMA) which is a more recent technique. The OFDM radar processing will be described in Section 5.2.1. FMA is described in Section 5.2.2.

In D1.1, the maximum time interval between sensing symbols is 0.83ms. During that time interval, 20% is allocated to sensing (see Figure 3.10). As a result, the transceiver can work in radar mode during 0.16ms. Both OFDM and FMA radars have continuous window of 0.16ms to operate and the beginning of each window is separated by 0.83ms. The system will accumulate $M=24$ of those snapshots to perform Doppler processing (see D1.1).

Sensing specification	
Range (R_u)	25m
Range resolution (R_r)	0.5m
Spatial/Angular resolution	6°
Velocity Resolution (v_r)	0.5m/s
Unambiguous Velocity (v_u)	6m/s (<i>Slow Vehicular AMR</i>)
Signal Bandwidth	400MHz
SINR (<i>after range processing</i>)	15dB

Figure 3.9 Sensing specification for the use-case scenario (from D1.1)

Sensing Signal Parameters @15GHz	
Maximum time interval between sensing symbols	$T_{r,max} = \frac{c}{4v_u f_c} = 0.83ms$
Minimum time interval between sensing symbols	$T_{r,min} = \frac{2R_u}{c} = 172ns$
Minimum sensing frame/burst duration	$T_{f,min} = \frac{c}{2v_r f_c} = 20ms$
Minimum Bandwidth	$BW_{reqd.} = \frac{c}{2R_r} = 300MHz$
Ratio of sensing to communication signal in time	20%

Figure 3.10 Sensing signal timing based on the specification (from D1.1)

3.4. Frequency synchronization and phase noise

Frequency synchronization is tightly coupled with time synchronization. As described in deliverable D1.1, the total time offset $\Delta T(\tau)$ of a free-running frequency synthesizer with respect to absolute time τ can be modeled as [Riley, 2008]:

$$\Delta T(\tau) = T_0 + \frac{\Delta f}{f} \tau + \frac{1}{2} D \tau^2 + T \sigma_x(\tau) \quad (3.1)$$

where T_0 is the initial time offset, $\Delta f/f$ is the fractional frequency offset, D is the frequency drift and $T \sigma_x(\tau)$ is the TDEV. Assuming that frequency aging is not dominant, the most dominant error sources are the fractional frequency offset $\Delta f/f$ and the TDEV $T \sigma_x(\tau)$.

As described in deliverable D1.1, the maximum acceptable time error is $\pm 4ps$ to allow coherent D-MIMO. If we consider this as the peak-peak value of a Gaussian random distribution, and aims for 3-4 sigma design, we put our design goal at $\pm 1ps$. As seen in the above equation for $\Delta T(\tau)$, the dominant time error sources due to the fractional frequency offset increases for longer free-running time τ . Although not directly visible in the equation, the same holds ultimately for TDEV. This puts constraints on the synchronization interval, fractional frequency offset and TDEV. These requirements are coupled. Having a shorter synchronization interval puts lower requirements on the

fractional frequency offset and TDEV, while having longer synchronization interval makes the requirements on fractional frequency offset and TDEV higher.

Let's for now assume that frequency synchronization is less critical than the TDEV of the local reference (we will verify this assumption at the end of this paragraph). The TDEV can be calculated with the MDEV $M\sigma_y(\tau)$ (Modified Allan Deviation), while MDEV can be calculated by integrating the phase noise $S_\phi(f)$ up to the highest relevant frequency f_h [Riley, 2008]:

$$T\sigma_x(\tau) = \frac{\tau}{\sqrt{3}} M\sigma_y(\tau), \quad (3.2)$$

$$M\sigma_y^2(\tau) = 2 \int_0^{f_h} \frac{f^2}{f_0^2} S_\phi(f) \frac{\sin^4 \pi \tau f}{(\pi \tau f)^2} df. \quad (3.3)$$

This is applied to a phase noise model of our target reference PLL, including a model of the intended Crystal Oscillator (XO) reference, which is subject to frequency wander noise (proportional to f^{-3}). The assumed phase noise profile is shown in Figure 3.11, with piece-wise asymptotic approximation lines in dashed-green. The corresponding MDEV is shown in Figure 3.12 and the resulting TDEV in Figure 3.13.

Figure 3.11 Measured phase noise of the reference-XO with asymptotic approximation lines (dashed green).

Figure 3.12 Simulated Modified Allan Deviation (MDEV) of the PLL.

Figure 3.13 Simulated Time Deviation (TDEV) of the PLL.

As the TDEV at an interval τ directly corresponds to the rms time error after a free-running time τ , we can see from Figure 3.13 that the maximum τ to stay below ~ 1 ps is in the order of 0.5ms. The TDEV is mostly limited by the f^{-3} phase noise (flicker frequency noise) of the crystal reference, causing the large increase when τ is larger than 0.1 ms. Lowering this deviation is not trivial, as f^{-3} phase noise originates from crystal physics, and hence exists in all crystal references. Therefore, taking some margin, we assume that a synchronization interval in the order of 1ms is required for the system to maintain synchronization around 1ps.

When we set the synchronization interval to 1ms, we can also calculate the maximum allowable fractional frequency error such that the time error stays below 1ps. This equals 1 ppb, corresponding to 30 fractional bits in the FCW of the fractional-N PLL. This 1ppb fits well with the frequency error derivation made in deliverable [6G-REFERENCE D1.1, 2024].

Summarizing, we conclude that we need to correct for time drift due to crystal flicker frequency noise about once every 0.5ms to keep TDEV below 1psec. About 30 fractional bits will be needed in the fractional-N XO-PLL synthesizer to keep frequency error below target 1ppb.

3.5. Time synchronization

To achieve robust time synchronization between all nodes and precise time-of-flight (ToF) measurements, we plan to implement a novel signal processing algorithm that we designate as “Transient Correlator” (or “T-Correlator” for short), which is based on the generalized likelihood ratio test (GLRT) and outperforms the current state-of-the-art. Traditionally, time synchronization is achieved via peak detection after cross-correlating the received signal with a known pseudo-random synchronization sequence. Unlike

existing solutions, which model sequence misalignments as Gaussian noise of unknown variance or ignore it altogether, we propose to treat it explicitly, deriving a test statistic $S(\mathbf{y}_{d'})$ that considers every possible integer sample shift v of the synchronization sequence \mathbf{s} , when correlating it with the sampled baseband received signal $\mathbf{y}_{d'}$ for time instant d' :

$$S(\mathbf{y}_{d'}) = \left(\frac{|\mathbf{s}^H \mathbf{y}_{d'}|^2}{\|\mathbf{s}\|^2} - \max_{0 < v < T-1} \frac{|\mathbf{s}_{-v}^H \mathbf{y}_{d'}|^2}{\|\mathbf{s}_{-v}\|^2} \right) \underset{H_0}{\overset{H_1}{\gtrless}} N_0 \cdot \log(\tau). \quad (3.4)$$

If this statistic exceeds the noise-dependent threshold given by the right-hand side of the above inequality, then the synchronization sequence is assumed to be present at time instant d' . The threshold can be tuned by varying the τ parameter between 0 and 1 to achieve different false alarm/missed detection trade-offs. It should also be emphasized that such a test statistic does not depend on any channel gain or its distribution and, thus, has the property of monotonically decreasing error probability for increasing SNR, which allows us to set the threshold τ only once for a desired point on the receiver operating curve (ROC) – i.e., a balance between the aforementioned probability of missed detection and the probability of false alarm. As demonstrated by some preliminary simulation results, illustrated below, the proposed method outperforms the conventional correlation-based procedure for varying SNRs, showing an improved ROC in every scenario.

Figure 3.14 Receiver Operating Curve (ROC) for the traditional correlation-based (“Corr”) time synchronization algorithm and the proposed GLRT-based algorithm (“GLRT”) in Rayleigh-fading channels for different SNRs.

4. Simulation chain

4.1. Channel simulations

In line with 6G-REFERENCE's use-case scenarios, and leveraging REMCOM's Wireless InSite [Remcom, 2025], wireless channels were simulated for a factory hall. A detailed 3D model of the environment was developed, as seen in Figure 4.1, allowing us to obtain realistic channel impulse responses by employing ray-tracing techniques.

Figure 4.1 3D model of the factory hall scenario used in REMCOM's Wireless InSite software to simulate ray-traced wireless propagation channels.

To simulate UEs, grids of uniformly spaced receiver points, each equipped with a single omnidirectional antenna, were added 1.2m above each floor of the building.

Furthermore, nine distinct RUs, acting as transceivers, were added to the scene (highlighted in blue in Figure 4.1), and each was equipped with an 8x4 patch antenna array, resembling a typical D-MIMO indoor deployment scenario characterized by dense multi-path. RUs near the walls were angled down by 45° and the centre ceiling-mounted RUs were angled directly downward (by 90°). To ensure universal coverage, RUs in corners were also rotated either left or right by an additional 45° . As depicted in Figure 4.2, the uniformity of this coverage was verified by simulating the minimum path loss at every UE from any array element of any RU (resembling selection combining).

Figure 4.2 Minimum path loss from any UE to any RU in the factory hall scenario using selection combining.

With such a setup, we characterized the channel from each antenna m of each transmitter a to each antenna n of each receiver b via its continuous time impulse response, given by

$$h_{a,m,b,n}(\tau) = \sum_{l=1}^L \alpha_{a,m,b,n,l} \cdot e^{-j\phi_{a,m,b,n,l}} \cdot \delta(\tau - \tau_{a,m,b,n,l}),$$

where $\alpha_{a,m,b,n,l}$ denotes the gain of the l th path in the link $a, m \rightarrow b, n$, $\phi_{a,m,b,n,l}$ the phase of that path and $\tau_{a,m,b,n,l}$ its delay.

With this information, two datasets were created. The first dataset, the **RU-to-RU CIR dataset** characterizes all RU-to-RU links and consists of a data tensor of size $9 \times 32 \times 9 \times 32 \times 250 \times 2$ (354MB), where the first and third dimensions correspond to the number of RUs, the second and fourth dimensions to the number of antennas of each RU, the fifth dimension to the largest number of multi-path components (MPCs) between any two links and the last dimension to the delay and complex coefficient characterizing each MPC (with phase and gain merged into a single parameter). Conversely, the second dataset, the **RU-to-UE CIR dataset**, holds the impulse responses for all RU-UE links and has a similar structure to the first, except that the third and fourth dimensions are now merged into a single dimension of size 13056 (the total number of UEs) and the maximum number of MPCs is lower (55), resulting in a data tensor of size $9 \times 32 \times 13056 \times 55 \times 2$ (3.1GB). Besides the channel impulse responses, each dataset also contains the position of all considered transmitter and receiver elements in a cartesian coordinate system centered at lower left corner of the 3D model from the perspective depicted in Figure 4.1, serving as the ground-truth for validating future signal processing algorithms, such as algorithms for positioning and direction-of-arrival-estimation.

The main purpose of these datasets is to provide a modular and standardized way to derive metrics to guide system design or measure its expected performance, such as channel capacity for a given placement of RUs or achievable rates and interference mitigation under different pre-coding/beamforming strategies. Simultaneously, they will allow us to test, under realistic conditions, the performance of application-specific signal processing techniques, such as the proposed GLRT-based time synchronization algorithm of section 3.5.

It should be noted that, for most experiments, an intermediate discretization step is required to fully exploit the dataset. Namely, we create the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) of the channel's baseband representation, $\tilde{h}_{a,m,b,n}[k]$, assuming an N point frequency grid $\mathbf{f}_{sc} = \left[-\frac{f_s}{2} \quad -\frac{f_s}{2} + \frac{f_s}{N-1} \quad \dots \quad \frac{f_s}{2} - \frac{f_s}{N-1} \quad \frac{f_s}{2} \right]$, where f_s denotes the sampling frequency. Denoting $f_{sc,k}$ as the k th element of \mathbf{f}_{sc} , this DFT is computed as:

$$\tilde{h}_{a,m,b,n}[k] = \sum_{l=1}^L \alpha_{a,m,b,n,l} \cdot e^{-j\phi_{a,m,b,n,l}} \cdot e^{-j2\pi f_{sc,k} l / f_s}.$$

The frequency domain representation can then be converted back to the time domain using the IDFT and some suitable windowing function to obtain the discretized channel impulse response (CIR) $h_{a,m,b,n}[n]$ or, alternatively, it can be multiplied element-wise by the transmitted signal to obtain the received signal directly in the frequency domain. This difference between the continuous time CIR $h_{a,m,b,n}(\tau)$ and its discretized version $h_{a,m,b,n}[n]$ is illustrated in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3 Effect of channel impulse response discretization.

This is precisely the general framework that allows us to test any algorithm that must deal with the propagation of a signal through a wireless channel, including how multi-path effects might distort it or how much a neighboring transmitter might interfere with the reception of the signal of interest. One can also aggregate $\tilde{h}_{a,m,b,n}[k]$ for all antennas

M_T of transmitter a and all antennas M_R of receiver b , obtaining the full MIMO channel matrix $\tilde{H}_{a,b,k}$ for frequency $f_{sc,k}$ as:

$$\tilde{H}_{a,b,k} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{h}_{a,1,b,1}[k] & \tilde{h}_{a,1,b,2}[k] & \cdots & \tilde{h}_{a,1,b,M_R}[k] \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \tilde{h}_{a,M_T,b,1}[k] & \tilde{h}_{a,M_T,b,2}[k] & \cdots & \tilde{h}_{a,M_T,b,M_R}[k] \end{bmatrix}$$

When using a multi-carrier modulation such as OFDM, this channel matrix represents the flat-fading channel coefficients between each TX-RX antenna pair on the k th sub-carrier (assuming the sub-carrier frequency grid is the same as f_{sc} above). This is also the representation that allows us to easily compute the channel capacity, one of the guiding metrics mentioned above. We start by computing the capacity for a single sub-carrier using the standard expression for a MIMO channel without water-filling:

$$C_{a,b,k} = B_{sc} \cdot \sum_i \log_2 \left(1 + \lambda_{k,i} \frac{P_{TX}}{M_T \cdot N_0} \right),$$

where B_{sc} denotes the sub-carrier spacing, P_{TX} the total transmit power, M_T the number of transmit antennas, N_0 the thermal noise power computed for a bandwidth B_{sc} and $\lambda_{k,i}$ the i th eigenvalue of $\tilde{H}_{a,b,k} \cdot \tilde{H}_{a,b,k}^H$. Then, to obtain the total channel capacity, we simply sum over all sub-carriers:

$$C_{a,b} = \sum_k B_{sc} \cdot \sum_i \log_2 \left(1 + \lambda_{k,i} \frac{P_{TX}}{M_T \cdot N_0} \right)$$

The same strategy can be employed to determine the achievable rates when using different pre-coding techniques. As an example, take zero-forcing (ZF) pre-coding. Provided the transmitter knows the channel $\tilde{H}_{a,b,k}$, the ZF pre-coding matrix W is given by

$$W = \gamma \cdot \tilde{H}_{a,b,k}^+,$$

where $\tilde{H}_{a,b,k}^+$ denotes the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse of $\tilde{H}_{a,b,k}$ and γ is a scaling factor given by $\sqrt{P_{TX}/\text{Tr}\left(\left(\tilde{H}_{a,b,k} \cdot \tilde{H}_{a,b,k}^H\right)^{-1}\right)}$, enforcing the total transmit power (P_{TX}) constraint. In this scenario, the SNR of each spatial stream is the same and given by $SNR_{ZF,a,b} = \gamma^2/N_0$ so the achievable rate can be simply computed as

$$C_{ZF,a,b} = B_{sc} \cdot M_T \cdot \log_2(1 + SNR_{ZF,a,b}).$$

These are only illustrative examples, and the same type of analysis can be extended to other pre-coding strategies at transmitter or equalization strategies at the receiver, such as Wiener filtering, and even scenarios where two or more RUs are transmitting simultaneously, such as in the envisioned full-duplex TDSYNC protocol for time

synchronization. Ultimately, this simulation methodology can be leveraged to accurately measure the performance of any implemented signal processing algorithms and accurately quantify the impact of challenging operating conditions, such as the mutual RU interference that was just mentioned. To further illustrate this point, the empirical cumulative distribution function (CDF) for the channel capacity, with and without water-filling, and the achievable rate for AP-to-AP communication using ZF pre-coding with none, 1 or 2 interfering links was simulated for the factory hall environment of Figure 4.1, and it can be examined in Figure 4.4. To further illustrate this point, the empirical cumulative distribution function (CDF) for the channel capacity, with and without water-filling, and the achievable rate for AP-to-AP communication using ZF pre-coding with none, 1 or 2 interfering links was simulated for the factory hall environment of Figure 4.1, and it can be examined in Figure 4.4. For the channel capacity and ZF pre-coding with no interference, the CDF was obtained by considering every possible RU-to-RU link, while for ZF pre-coding with 1 or 2 interfering links, all possible combinations of interfering links were also considered, resulting in more samples and smoother curves. The exact and approximate versions of the achievable rates differ only in the way the interference effect was modeled: while in the approximate case it was treated as additional spatially uncorrelated Gaussian noise of equivalent power, in the exact case the full interference covariance matrix was taken into account.

Figure 4.4 CDF of channel capacity and achievable rate with ZF pre-coding for AP-to-AP communication in the factory hall environment.

4.2. RF front-end macro-model and Simulations

When designing an RF front-end with a cascade of functional blocks, several design trade-offs must be made. For instance, receiver noise figure is typically dominated by the Low Noise Amplifier (LNA) but also has non-negligible contributions due to e.g. antenna filter losses and mixer noise. More LNA-gain is good for mixer noise, but harms receiver linearity. To simulate these interdependencies, it is very useful to have a simplified macro-model of the functional blocks including the main impairments, e.g. model port impedance, gain, noise and nonlinearity. This allows for design space exploration and optimization of block-parameter choices. Moreover, higher-level system simulations can start early in parallel to block-circuit designs, leveraging the macro-model. Furthermore, when a circuit-level design becomes available, the macro-model of a block can be replaced by a more refined circuit model, while the macro-models can be used to simulate this circuit in a realistic system environment. Hence our goal is to develop such a macro-model for the RF front-end.

4.2.1. Objectives

In this section, we will describe the methodology put in place to simulate the RF chain. Our RF design methodology consists of three steps:

- Creation of a behavioral macro model to specify, verify, and optimize high-level performance.
- Simulation of the top-cell in schematic view for all blocks.
- Implementation and electromechanical extraction to validate performance.

First, we created a behavioral model to simulate the behavior of each block, in terms of power gain (linearity issues are taken into account) and noise, according to the frequencies and input powers involved. This RFIC model will be combined with an electrical model of phased-array antennas (as described in deliverable D1.2, section 3.1). The main objectives of this project are:

- Highlight Tx/Rx coupling issues and find the best RFIC configurations in terms of phase shift to address in the antenna array.
- Validate the high-level performance simulations described in Deliverable D1.2 in Section 3.2.

4.2.2. RF front-end description

We design an RF front-end IC, targeting system goals set in the D1.1 report and the various specifications set by the link budget (section 3.1.3). This transceiver should operate in Rx or Tx mode and be compatible with the requirements of full duplex.

Five main functionalities should be present in this RF chip. The proposed RF front-end is shown in figure 4.5. It is composed of:

- A fully differential duplexer (Depicted as Coupler + SW in Figure 4.5) operating at 15GHz, BW=400MHz, and with high level of isolation between Tx and Rx. Although RF-SIC is challenging to implement in an array context and was not relied on in the link budget in section 3.2.3 (RF-SIC = 0dB in Figure 3.8), this can be reconsidered later if the Tx/Rx isolation performance is not sufficient.
- A Power Amplifier (PA) operating at 15GHz, BW=400MHz, with a mean power of 0dBm and an Output third-order Intercept Point OIP3 of 25dBm.
- A Low-Noise Amplifier operating at 15GHz, BW=400MHz, with Input third-order Intercept Point IIP3 > 0dBm.
- A Tx Up-conversion mixer with input bandwidth of 1GHz, an LO frequency of 14GHz and an output operating frequency of 15GHz. The conversion gain and the Output third-order Intercept Point OIP3 are fixed respectively to 5dB and to 18dBm, compatible with an OIP3 including PA of +25dBm.
- An Rx Down-conversion mixer operating at an input frequency of 15GHz, an LO frequency of 14GHz and an output bandwidth of 1GHz. The conversion gain and the input third-order Intercept Point IIP3 are fixed respectively to 3dB and to 11dBm.
- An LO Phase Shifter implemented in the LO path, allowing for beamforming functionality. This can support spatial SIC functionality if necessary. Phase Shifters tend to be lossy and occupy large die size due to the use of inductors. To reduce this negative impact, we have not implemented them in the RF path where loss directly degrades noise figure, but rather in the large-signal LO path. The specification for this block is ongoing, but we have set the phase step and the phase range respectively at 5.63° and $0-360^\circ$.

Figure 4.5 Block Diagram Description of RF Front-End Module

4.2.3. RF front-end macro-model

One of the largest concerns in full duplex is self-interference (SI), i.e. Tx-power and Tx-EVM couple back to the receiver and interfere with the much weaker receive signal to be received. Many solutions have been presented to mitigate SI in the RF domain [Kolodziej, 2019] by creating a copy of the expected transmit SI signal and subtracting it from the received signal. Nevertheless, as already mentioned RF-SIC will not be implemented in a first step.

A technique that fits well to a phased array application is proposed in [Doane, 2016]. The paper demonstrates how digital beamforming, and cancellation enables adjacent transmitting and receiving sub-arrays to operate simultaneously in the same frequency band without a significant reduction in performance. We propose to implement this technique to mitigate self-interferences in our demonstrator.

A high-level model of the whole 8x4 antenna array has been made by antenna experts (section 3.1). From our side, we have created a behavioural RFIC model implementing all functionalities of the RF part. The main objective of this behavioural modelling is to predict the optimal phase and amplitude of the interference cancellation signal.

This behavioural model also represents the first step in the development of the RFIC. For each block in the RFIC system model, shown in Figure 4.6, a macro-model is implemented to model its function and key impairments like e.g. noise and nonlinearity.

Figure 4.6 Top-cell of RF front-end macro model.

Each behavioural model is coded in Verilog-A. For some less critical functions, we used ideal components. For example, the non-crucial duplexer (depicted to the left of the Figure 4.7) is implemented using coupled inductors to model its basic behaviour. If the antenna impedance is accurately mimicked by the Variable Balanced Network, coupling between the transmitter and receiver is minimized.

Below find some of the main characteristics found by simulations using the models:

- Full Differential duplexer:

Figure 4.7 Left — S-Parameter test bench for simulations performed to evaluate the duplexer model. Right – Simulation results describing the return loss of each port, the insertion losses for both Rx and Tx (more than 3dB), and the isolation between Tx and Rx can reach -51dB with $Z_{BN}=40-j19\Omega$

- **Power Amplifier:** As shown in Figure 4.6, the Verilog-A model of the PA output signal takes into account power gain, noise figure, input- and output impedance mismatch, and the 1dB compression point. Currently, we have not yet implemented the impact on PA output power due to output impedance mismatch, potentially caused by neighbouring antenna element coupling and antenna array beam steering. We are exploring a technique integrated into the duplexer to isolate the PA from such impedance mismatch effects.
- **Low-Noise Amplifier:** As shown in Figure 4.6, the Verilog-A model of the LNA output signal takes into account the power gain, noise figure, input- and output impedance mismatch, and the 1dB compression point.
- **Tx and Rx Mixer:** We use the same behavioural model for Rx and Tx Mixer. we consider in a first approximation that the theoretical phenomena are the same. When used in a receiver, signals are inputted into a mixer's RF and LO ports to produce an output at the IF signal port. When used in a transmitter, signals are inputted into a mixer's IF and LO ports to produce an output at the RF signal port. We extended an ideal mixer model in Verilog-A with filtering as filtering is key for superheterodyne architectures. As saturation due to SI might be a problem, we also added saturation due to third-order nonlinearity along with IIP3 and noise.
- **LO Phase Shifter:** In order to carry out this function, we will use a Vector Modulator topology. Initially, we simply modelled this combining two behavioural blocks: a Phase Shifter and an Attenuator.

4.2.4. Simulation Results

We have created a test bench (depicted in the Figure 4.8) allowing us to characterize both a single Tx and Rx and to carry out a co-simulation of several Tx and Rx in parallel loaded by the 64-port antenna model, already described in the previous paragraphs.

Regarding the simulation of the TRx standalone, all macro blocks are supplied separately with a voltage of 0.8V (can be changed according to design constraints). We applied a 50 Ohms port on the Tx IF input with a frequency of 500MHz and a variable power. We applied a 50 Ohms port on the Rx and Tx LO inputs with a frequency of 14.5GHz and an arbitrary input power of 20dBm. More, we put a 50 Ohms Rx port on the antenna input with a frequency of 14.8GHz and we have the possibility to vary the Rx power as we wish. And finally, a last 50 Ohms port at the output of the Rx chain in order to measure the received signal @ 300MHz.

Figure 4.8 Simulation Test bench of RF Front-End

The antenna was characterized using s-parameter simulation, allowing to evaluate Return Losses of the Tx at the IF port (500 MHz dip) and antenna ports (15GHz dip), as described in Figure 4.9.

Figure 4.9 Return loss of Tx and antenna ports (FLO=14.5GHz & FTX=500MHz)

A harmonic Balance Simulation has been performed in order to obtain power gains, power level, isolation, noise effects, and nonlinearity issues in the Tx and Rx. The main parameters in this simulation are:

Table 4-1: Tx Parameters used in the HB Simulation

Tx In Buffer Gain [dB]	Tx In Buffer OCP1 [dBm]	Tx Mixer Gain [dB]	Tx Mixer OCP1 [dBm]	Tx PA Gain [dB]	Tx PA OCP1 [dBm]
6	30	10	13.5	15	15

Table 4-2: Rx Parameters used in the HB Simulation

Rx LNA Gain [dB]	Tx LNA IIP3 [dBm]	Rx LNA NF [dB]	Rx Mixer Gain [dB]	Rx Mixer ICP1 [dBm]	Rx Mixer NF [dB]	Rx Out Buffer Gain [dB]	Rx Out Buffer NF [dB]	Rx Out Buffer ICP1 [dBm]

28	0	2.5	3	25	20	10	25	30
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In this nonlinearity analysis, we want to find the power level around the key fundamental frequencies for this kind of architecture. The frequency plan is described in the Table 4-3

Table 4-3: Frequency span of tones for the HB analysis – Freq. [1] = 100MHz (n° harmonics=6) - Freq. [2] = 14.5GHz (n° harmonics=5)

Freq [Hz]	Harmonic Combination [m n p]
0	[0 0 0]
100M	[1 0 0]
200M	[2 0 0]
300M	[3 0 0]
400M	[4 0 0]
500M	[5 0 0]
600M	[6 0 0]
14.0G	[-5 1 0]
14.1G	[-4 1 0]
14.2G	[-3 1 0]
14.3G	[-2 1 0]
14.4G	[-1 1 0]
14.5G	[0 1 0]
14.6G	[1 1 0]
14.7G	[2 1 0]
14.8G	[3 1 0]
14.9G	[4 1 0]
15G	[5 1 0]
28.6G	[-4 2 0]
28.7G	[-3 2 0]
28.8G	[-2 2 0]
28.9G	[-1 2 0]
29G	[0 2 0]
29.1G	[1 2 0]
29.2G	[2 2 0]
29.3G	[3 2 0]
29.4G	[4 2 0]
42.2G	[-3 3 0]
42.3G	[-2 3 0]
42.4G	[-1 3 0]
42.5G	[0 3 0]
42.6G	[1 3 0]
42.7G	[2 3 0]
42.8G	[3 3 0]
57.8G	[-2 4 0]
57.9G	[-1 4 0]
58.0G	[0 4 0]
58.1G	[1 4 0]
58.2G	[2 4 0]
72.4G	[-1 5 0]
72.5G	[0 5 0]
72.6G	[1 5 0]

The input tones of the HB simulation are defined as follow: the first is fixed at 100MHz, with 6 harmonics, and the second tone is FLO = 14.5GHz with 5 harmonics. By fixing these 2 tones, we obtain a spectral description shown in Table 43. This spectral combination allows an evaluation of the power levels with more accuracy, for signals, harmonics and also potential distortions in the Rx and Tx.

In this simulation, we were able to highlight the compression of the PA in the Tx chain. When the Tx input power increases, the PA gain remains at 15dB until the output power is close to 20dBm, as depicted in the Figure 4.10.

Figure 4.10 Harmonic Balance Simulation results of Tx Part – Inputs- and Outputs Power [dBm], and Power Gain [dB] vs. Tx Input Power [dBm].

Figure 4.11 and Figure 4.12 shows that the Rx power level increases sharply near the maximum Tx power. Indeed, the behavioural model of the Power Amplifier takes into account the increasing level of the distortion arising from compression. Beyond the compression point, the level of the power increases strongly in the Power Amplifier output for all frequencies simulated around the 15GHz Tx Fundamental frequency. In the Figure 4.11, we can see the impact of the PA distortion on the 14.8GHz harmonic (Which is also the Rx signal) through the duplexer.

Moreover, the considered duplexer model is a small signal version. i.e. the Tx and Rx isolation is not effective when the input power coming from PA increases in the duplexer. In the next version we will replace this duplexer model by a large signal one allowing better Tx and Rx isolation.

Figure 4.11 Power Level [dBm] on the Antenna Port @ Rx and Tx frequencies vs. Tx input power [dBm].

Figure 4.12 Power Level [dBm] on the LNA Input @ Rx and Tx Frequencies vs. Tx Input Power [dBm].

Figure 4.13 Harmonic Balance Simulation Results of Rx Part – Inputs and Outputs Power [dBm], and Power Gain [dB] vs. Tx Input Power [dBm].

Another harmonic Balance Simulation has been performed to evaluate Power Gains, Power level, isolation, noise effects, and nonlinearity in the Tx and Rx according to Rx input power (PRX) variation. The goal is to check whether the specified compression point

of each Rx chain block is well chosen to avoid saturation issues in the LNA and in this Rx chain.

Figure 4.14 Harmonic Balance Simulation results of Tx Inputs and Outputs Power [dBm], and Tx Power Gain [dB] vs -78dBm < PRX < -25dBm variation [dBm].

Figure 4.15 Power Level [dBm] on the Antenna and Input LNA Ports @ Rx and Tx Frequencies vs. Tx Input Power [dBm].

Figure 4.16 Harmonic Balance Simulation Results of Rx Inputs and Outputs Power [dBm], and Rx Power Gain [dB] vs -78dBm < PRX < -25dBm variation [dBm].

4.3. OFDM Radar Sensing Simulations

This section reports on the outcomes from study based on the conceptualization and simulation of radar signal processing in an ISAC rationale. The architecture of the simulated sensing system has been implemented using a signal, which is a communications waveform, OFDM, but without strict constraints thanks to the time separation (80% of the time slots for communication and for 20% sensing). This choice allows a configuration of the signal parameters able to achieve the required radar performance. The processing chain consists of range/Doppler mapping and angle of arrival estimation. We assume that, based on a communication-centric rationale, the radar transmitter sends a waveform suitable for the employed communication hardware, which is hence known by the radar receiver. The simulated radar tasks are based on ad-hoc algorithms. Range and Doppler frequencies estimations are noticeable studying the radar ambiguity function [Palamà, 2025]. The effect of the antenna array size on spatial resolution is evaluated with simulations carried out using different beamforming solutions.

System model

This simulation is based on an OFDM modulation technique. Design parameters are reported in Table 4-4. Every OFDM frame consists of N sub-carriers and M OFDM symbols. The l -th OFDM symbol contains N complex modulation symbols $c_{k,l}$. For the OFDM modulation, the following parameters are relevant:

- Centre frequency: f_0
- Frequency sub-carrier spacing: Δf
- Length of the guard interval: T_G
- Length of the cyclic prefix: T_{CP}
- Number of subcarriers: N (here obtained from the RF bandwidth ($B=N \Delta f$))
- Number of symbols per frame: M

The total duration of one OFDM symbol is: $T_0 = 1/\Delta f + T_G$

Table 4-4: Signal simulation parameters

Input Signal Parameter	Value
Subcarrier bandwidth (MHz)	6
Cyclic prefix time (s)	0
Number of subcarriers	64
Number of symbols in frame	24

The radar waveform is continuously transmitted and for this reason we set the cyclic prefix to zero.

The OFDM frame is described by a $[N \times M]$ complex matrix,

$$\mathbf{F}_{TX} = \begin{bmatrix} c_{0,0} & \cdots & c_{0,M-1} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ c_{N-1,0} & \cdots & c_{N-1,M-1} \end{bmatrix}$$

We assume that the modulation symbol is normalized to unit power. To create the transmitted time domain signal, $s_T(t)$, every column of \mathbf{F}_{TX} is transformed by a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). The results for the individual columns are then concatenated.

Figure 4.17 OFDM radar transceiver block diagram.

In the presence of one reflecting target, a time- and frequency-shifted signal is received:

$$r(t) = \alpha s_T(t - \tau) e^{j2\pi f_D t} + w(t)$$

where the complex factor α is the complex backscattered factor associated with the radar target, τ its round-trip delay and f_D its Doppler frequency.

The amplitude antenna pattern along the azimuth direction θ is denoted as $|G(\theta)|$. The noise, $w(t)$, is modelled as an additive white Gaussian random process of variance equal to the noise power (P_N). The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is calculated using the radar equation and it includes the RCS of the target.

The Doppler shift causes a row-wise oscillation depending on the frequency f_D , $e^{j2\pi l T_0 f_D}$, whereas the delay causes a phase shift estimated with $e^{-j2\pi k \tau \Delta f}$.

The received signal matrix associated with one target is thus given by

$$(\mathbf{F}_{RX})_{k,l} = (\mathbf{F}_{TX})_{k,l} e^{j2\pi l T_0 f_D} e^{-j2\pi k \tau \Delta f} e^{j\varphi} + (\mathbf{W})_{k,l}$$

Where \mathbf{F}_{RX} is the matrix representing the received signal and $(\mathbf{W})_{k,l}$ the corresponding noise contribution.

Range-Doppler processing

The first operation consists of an element-wise division of the received signal matrix, after OFDM demodulation, \mathbf{F}_{RX} , by the transmitted matrix, \mathbf{F}_{TX} . The matrix resulting from this division is:

$$(\mathbf{F}_{DIV})_{k,l} = (\mathbf{F}_{RX})_{k,l} / (\mathbf{F}_{TX})_{k,l}$$

The maximum likelihood estimator (MLE) of the delay and Doppler shift is given by computing first the Fourier Transform (implemented by FFT) on the rows of the matrix \mathbf{F}_{DIV} (i.e. symbols of the OFDM frame), then the Inverse Fourier Transform (implemented by Inverse FFT, IFFT) on the columns of \mathbf{F}_{DIV} (i.e. subcarriers of the OFDM frame). The first FFT of length M will resolve objects in the Doppler dimension, whereas the IFFT of length N is implemented to resolve targets in the delay (i.e. range) dimension. The range Doppler map is hence represented through N delay and M frequency steps, τ and f_D , respectively. The range r is given by $r = (c \tau / 2)$, where c is the speed of light. The delay-Doppler map is then a (N, M) matrix.

The processing scheme assumes knowledge of the transmitted symbols and processes the received signals as following:

- (i) OFDM demodulation
- (ii) element-wise division by OFDM symbol
- (iii) row- (symbol)-wise FFT (Doppler processing)
- (iv) column (subcarrier)-wise IFFT (range processing)

The output consists of a range-Doppler map with a coherent processing interval equal to the OFDM frame duration.

In Figure 4.18, the geometry of the radar simulation is depicted.

Figure 4.18: Geometry of the simulated radar acquisition.

DoA estimation

The simulator can use different types of antennas. In these simulations we estimate the DoA assuming that the antenna system consists of a planar array of radiative elements. In general, DoA estimation techniques in digital arrays can be split into two groups: beam scanning and nulling. In beam scanning, here selected, an array beam is scanned through the angular region of interest and the received power in each angle is used to detect sources. Different beamformers can be used as the phased array beamformer or the minimum variance distortionless response (MVDR) beamformer, also known as [Capon, 1969] beamformer. The angular resolution of these methods is constrained by the array beamwidth. The Capon beamformer is based on estimating the covariance matrix of the received snapshots (symbols received for each antenna), and then blocking all directions present on the covariance matrix while pointing to the direction of interest. The covariance matrix is estimated using a finite number of snapshots, i.e., different combinations of the array elements via spatial smoothing technique (see Section 5.2 for more details). This is possible thanks to the flexibility of the 6G antenna system.

Being the complex backscattered factor associated with the radar target, using the phased array beamformer for scanning the region of interest, we can write

$$\mathbf{b}(\theta, \varphi) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_a}} e^{j \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} s(\theta, \varphi)}$$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_a}} e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}(x\sin(\theta)\cos(\varphi)+y\sin(\theta)\sin(\varphi))}$$

where N_a is the number of elements in the array, \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} the vectors with the horizontal and vertical coordinates of the element positions, and θ and φ the zenith (complementary of elevation) and azimuth pointing angles.

In our simulations, all elements in the same column are driven with the same amplitude and phase, thus we only perform beamforming in the azimuth plane. Therefore, a two-dimensional search space is assumed, thus the zenith angle ϑ was set at 0. In the system concept here described the scanning on the azimuth plane is done purely in the digital domain. A range-Doppler processing is performed for each antenna element, then the DoA estimation is performed on the resulting complex range-Doppler matrices. The DoA estimation performs the scanning by combining the range-Doppler matrices with the required beamformer.

Table 4-5: Radar simulation parameters

Radar Parameter	Value
Bandwidth (MHz)	300
Centre frequency (GHz)	15
Transmitted power (dBm)	13
System Temperature (K)	290
Tx Antenna gain (dB)	5
Rx Antenna gain (dB)	10
Noise figure (dB)	3

Results from a simulation carried out using typical design parameters resumed in Table 4-5 are shown. Those numbers are given as example to show the capabilities of the simulator. Figure 4.19 shows the range/azimuth power map obtained with a target located in coordinates (15m,0m) and the radar in (0m,10m) (see figure 4.17). Two beamformer types (Chebyshev and Capon) were used, and a (4x4) array.

Figure 4.19 shows the simulation results obtained using an 8x4 array, the array targeted in 6G-REFERENCE. The single range and azimuth profiles are also shown to allow estimating the range and the azimuth resolution respectively. The results are very close to the 0.5m and 6 degree requirements of D1.1 [6G-REFERENCE D1.1,2024].

Figure 4.19: – Range/azimuth power maps obtained with different antenna systems: a) Chebyshev array; b) Capon. Number of elements: 4x4.

Figure 4.20 – a) Range/azimuth power map obtained with Capon beamformer, number of elements: (8x4); b) range cut of the map.

5. Signal Processing for Applications

5.1. Communication

5.1.1. Baseband simulation

To validate the specifications established at the budget link level given in the and distribute the overall transmit and receive requirements over different building blocks, it is relevant to take the baseband processing into account, as it will compensate for a significant part of the RF impairments. As an example, the phase noise will be reduced by the CFO (Carrier Frequency Offset) and CPE (Common Phase Error) cancelling loop, while I/Q mismatch will also be compensated. Moreover, we will consider predistortion to improve the power efficiency of the power amplifier. The specifications of the RF building blocks will have to be established according to the targeted BER (Bit Error Rate) in agreement with the baseband processing algorithm. For that purpose, we have developed a system simulation chain, which includes the RF impairments depicted at the baseband simulation level. This simulation chain is described briefly below. This baseband simulation chain is a classical OFDM system simulation chain, updated with the characteristics of the signal given in D1.1.

Figure 5.1 Baseband Simulation Chain with RF impairments models.

This main components in the communication chain, depicted in Figure 5.1, are:

- Emitter: channel coding (convolutional codes), mapping (QAM modulation), spreading (OVSF codes), multiplexing, interleaving, OFDM modulation (IFFT) and insertion of a cyclic prefix (to avoid inter symbol interference)
- Channel : performing multi path (BRAN models) and adding white noise
- Receiver: guard interval removal, OFDM demodulation (FFT), de-interleaving, turbo equalisation based on channel estimation, de-spreading, de-mapping and decoding
- Sink and results: Bit Error Rate is calculated by Monte Carlo method
- RF front-end: The RF front-end module previously described has been added between propagation channel and receiver and between the propagation channel and transmitter to include impairments.

Analogue RF and digital baseband and their interaction are both modelled now.

5.1.2. Impairment modeling

Currently, several simulators can provide baseband models of RF impairments, just like MATLAB RF toolbox or others. Such libraries may be interesting from a signal processing point of view, but they also come with drawbacks since they are not based on a physical implementation. This can lead to misleading results, especially in a multi-antenna scheme. We hence prefer proprietary RF models which are related to the physical implementation of the building blocks. Figure 5.2 describes the simulated phase noise spectra obtained with different level of VCO phase noise filtered by a first order PLL.

Figure 5.2 VCO Phase noise filtered by a first order PLL

Different phenomena can be modelled in the phase noise model: flicker noise, Wiener noise, white noise and spurious and can be added for each building block.

Using these models, we can estimate the impact of RF impairments and check whether target block specifications in a realistic context are adequate for system performance.

5.1.3. Specification Methodology

Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) degradation at constant bit error rate (BER) is commonly used as a relevant characteristic for evaluating impairments in a communication system. Indeed, a certain BER is commonly required to guarantee a certain quality of service despite impairments. During functional operation, increasing transmit signal power or decreasing receiver noise level may be possible to compensate for performance degradations due to impairments. To design a robust system, it is important to budget for impairments as part of front-end specifications. A way to do that is by characterizing the effect of impairments on BER. The following methodology is followed:

- SNR is tuned so that the BER attains its targeting value (10^{-4})
- SNR is increased by x dB increasing signal power, which reduces BER
- RF impairments are added, and their parameters are tuned so that BER increases again up to its original target value
- The parameters thus obtained correspond to the x -dB degradation specification, allocated to this impairment

Figure 5.3 Methodology for extracting RF front-end specifications.

5.2. Sensing

5.2.1. OFDM radar processing

In order to design the OFDM radar waveform we will, first, consider an ideal analog radar front-end where the radar sensitivity is only limited by the thermal noise in the receiver. Then, we will evaluate the impact of different front-end impairments and propose mitigation techniques.

The SISO conventional OFDM radar block diagram is described on Figure 5.4. It starts by defining the frequency domain the frequency domain spectrum of the sequence to transmit. As we will see later, the choice of the frequency domain spectrum of the code sequence has a significant impact on the radar performances. This code sequence is converted into time domain via an IFFT. Each code sequence is composed by L_c samples. It is, then, repeated continuously to produce the time domain signal $b(n)$. This one is converted to an analog domain signal via a DAC and up-converted to the chosen carrier frequency.

On the receiver side, the signal at the output of ADC is divided in blocks of L_c samples, which will be used for range processing. Each group of N consecutive range profiles are accumulated coherently.

Figure 5.4: Conventional SISO OFDM radar transceiver block diagram.

From D1.1, we know that the 1dB compression point of the power amplifier is 15 dBm. As we will see later, the OFDM radar waveform will be designed such that it can be used at this operating point. If we assume an antenna gain of 3dB, including insertion loss, in order to target large field of view, we can estimate the measured power of a 0dBsm target at the input of the LNA of a single receiver:

$$P_R = P_T \frac{G_T G_R \lambda^2}{(4\pi)^3 R^4} \sigma_{rcs}^2$$

where P_R is the received power at LNA input

P_T is the power amplifier output power (15dBm)

G_T and G_R are the antenna gain on the transmitter and receiver side (3dB)

R is the target range (15m)

σ_{RCS}^2 is the target RCS (0dBsm)

λ is the wavelength (2cm)

This equation gives a receiver power of -90.5 dBm.

In order to get the SNR of that target, we also need to take into account the thermal noise in that same receiver. As we target a range resolution of 0.5m, the signal bandwidth is 300 MHz. This corresponds to the bandwidth covered by the occupied subcarriers. If we assume a total receiver noise figure of 10dB, the LNA input referred noise power is:

$$P_N = k_B T B F$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant

T is the temperature (we assume 298°K)

B is the signal bandwidth (300 MHz)

F is the receiver noise figure (6dB)

This equation gives a noise power of -79.1 dBm.

As a result, the target SNR is -11.4 dB. We can see that the SNR is negative, but this is very common in radar. In practice, the signal at ADC output will be processed with matched filters before applying a detection algorithm. Those different matched filters will increase the target SNR a lot. This is called the processing gain.

The maximum processing gain that we can achieve depends on the number of samples that the radar can accumulate before doing the detection. This is given by the observation window given to the radar.

In order to simplify the hardware, we can assume that the radar works in Time-Domain MIMO mode. This means that each transmitter works one after the other (see Figure 5.5). If we target a radar system with 4 transmitters and as each observation window for sensing is 0.16 ms to get a single range profile (see section 3.3), this means that the range processing can be done over 0.04ms for each transmitter. Usually, in radar processing, the detection is done after range and Doppler processing. This means that the targeted SNR will only benefit from range and Doppler processing gain. In practice, we can also apply a matched filter along the antennas dimension to get more processing gain before detection, but this increases the processing complexity a lot. Therefore, in this work, the

detection will be done after range and Doppler processing only. But, as we will see, this provides enough SNR.

Figure 5.5 TD-MIMO OFDM radar frame structure for 4 transmitters. L_c : code sequence length. N : number of coherent accumulations. T_c : DAC sampling period. N_{Tx} : Number of transmitters.

As we can see in Figure 5.5, each code sequence from each transmitter is repeated $N+1$ times instead of N times. This is because OFDM radars rely on the periodic transmission of the symbols. When we change the transmitter, this introduces a phase offset which breaks the periodicity. Therefore, in a group of $N+1$ repetitions of an OFDM symbol, the signal is periodic from the point of view of the second OFDM repetition but not from the point of view of the first one. The role of the first OFDM repetition is the same as a cyclic prefix in communication.

The signal processing from ADC to detection works in 3 steps: range processing – coherent accumulation – Doppler processing. Those steps are done N_{Tx} times per receiver as each receiver must process the signal coming from each transmitter.

As the radar must cover a maximum unambiguous range of 25m with a range resolution of 0.5m we need, at least $25m/0.5m=50$ range bins. This means that the OFDM symbols used for radar contain 50 occupied subcarriers to cover a bandwidth of 300 MHz. As a results, the range processing gain is $10 \log_{10} 50 = 17dB$.

As the duration of a single OFDM symbols is the inverse of the sub-carrier spacing and as the spacing is $\frac{300 MHz}{50} = 6 MHz$, this also means that the symbol duration is $0.1667\mu s$. As we have $40\mu s$ for a single range profile, we have enough time to transmit 239 code sequences. As we never process the first one, we have 238 range profiles to accumulate. This coherent accumulation provides a processing gain of $10 \log_{10} 238 = 23.8dB$.

In the following, we will use $N = 237$ and, therefore, repeat the code sequence $N + 1 = 238$ times. The loss in processing gain is negligible. The reason will become clearer once we have introduced the $\pi/2K$ modulation technique.

This means that after range processing and coherent accumulation, the total processing gain is 40.8 dB. This means that a 0 dBsm target at 13 m will have a SNR of 29.4 dB (see Figure 5.6). As we need at least 15 dB of SNR to detect a target (see D1.1), the range profiles after coherent accumulation provide enough SNR. As we have 14.4 dB higher than the requirement for detection, it means that we can relax the constraint on receiver noise figure. For example, if the receiver noise figure is 15 dB instead of 10 dB, the SNR after range processing and coherent accumulation will become 24.4 dB. We can see that the 5 dB loss in SNR still allows the detection of the 0 dBsm target at 13 m.

In practice, it is required to use a window before the IFFT on Figure 5.4 for better range sidelobe control. A Hann window has been used to generate the range profile on Figure 5.6. This introduces a SNR loss of 1.8 dB.

Another important point to note is the presence of a self-interference signal. This is the dominating peak on Figure 5.6. In this simulation, we assumed a coupling of -30dB between the transmitter and the receiver. As it only produces a single peak at very short range (where we do not expect to see a target), the presence of the self-interference signal does not affect the radar performances (if we neglect IQ imbalance and transceiver front-end non-linearity). The only source of signal degradation is, then, the thermal noise. As we will see in the next section, the combination of a strong self-interference signal and hardware impairment can degrade the signal if the transmitted waveform is not optimized.

Figure 5.6: Range profile after range processing and coherent accumulation.

Figure 5.7: SISO OFDM radar transceiver block diagram using pi/K modulation

In practice, the radar analog front-end has other non-idealities which can degrade the radar performances. The dominant ones in OFDM radar are: power amplifier non-linearity, IQ imbalance, receiver DC offset. We will see that we can mitigate all of them by waveform design.

IQ imbalance and receiver DC offset mitigation can be achieved with a technique called pi/K modulation [Bauduin, 2022] (see Figure 5.7). The benefit of this technique is that we can remove the artifact due to IQ imbalance and receiver DC offset without having to estimate them.

The pi/K modulation technique consists in multiplying the transmitted digital signal by a progressive phase rotation. As a result, the signal at the input of the DAC is not $b(n)$ anymore but:

$$s(n) = b(n)e^{j\frac{\pi}{K}n}$$

K is an arbitrary number chosen such that:

1. L_c is not a multiple of K
2. NL_c is a multiple of $2K$

As, in this project, we use $L_c = 64$ and $N = 237$, we can use $K = 1.5$. If N and L_c were both even numbers, we could not find a value of K which satisfies the two criteria above.

The benefit of π/K modulation is illustrated on Figure 5.8. We can see that, because of IQ imbalance, the self-interference signal produces range sidelobes, which are much higher than the target we want to detect. On the other hand, once we use the π/K modulation technique, the impact of IQ imbalance is removed, and the small target is visible again. It is important to note that we never tried to estimate the IQ imbalance parameters. The waveform became robust to IQ imbalance by design.

Figure 5.8: Range profile after range processing and coherent accumulation with and without π/K modulation in presence of IQ imbalance.

For the power amplifier non-linearity, a solution is to choose a waveform with low PAPR. As the radar and communication functionalities have to work in different time slots, we can define the OFDM radar waveform independently from the communication one. Therefore, we propose to use the P3 code sequence [Levanon, 2004]:

$$B_c(l) = e^{j\frac{\pi}{L_c}l^2}$$

where $B_c(l)$ is the spectrum of a single OFDM symbol and l is the sub-carrier index ($l = 0, \dots, L_c - 1$). This is the code sequence that we used to generate the range profiles on Figure 5.6 and Figure 5.8.

This one has CAZAC (Constant Amplitude Zero AutoCorrelation) property. The constant amplitude is interesting in frequency domain to avoid noise enhancement during range processing. The Zero AutoCorrelation also means that the IFFT of the signal is also constant amplitude. Therefore, P3 has low PAPR in the time domain (for a better robustness to power amplifier non-linearity) and a constant amplitude in the frequency domain to avoid noise enhancement during range processing.

As an example, if we use 4 transmitters and 4 receivers, we can create a virtual array of $K = 16$ elements under far-field conditions. If the spacing between the elements in the virtual array is $\frac{\lambda}{2}$ the aperture covered by the antennas array is $D = 8\lambda$. Therefore, if the angular processing is done with a matched filter (e.g. FFT), the angular resolution is $\Delta\theta = 1.22 \frac{\lambda}{D} \text{ rad} = 8.73^\circ$. Please note that this is twice the size of the proposed array.

In order to achieve the required resolution with a smaller aperture size, we can rely on super resolution algorithms such as root-MUSIC [Barabell, 1983]. The main benefit of root-MUSIC compared to MUSIC is that it also performs the detection. Alternatively, we can use Capon beamforming as discussed in 4.3. The benefit of Capon is that it does not require the knowledge of the number of targets.

Root-MUSIC will be applied on each range-Doppler cell where a detection occurred (this requires a SNR of, at least, 15dB). Unfortunately, this means that we are in the single snapshot scenario as we have only one sample per virtual antenna. As a result, the covariance matrix used by root-MUSIC is rank-1. It is therefore required to use the forward-backward spatial smoothing (FBSS) algorithm to increase the rank of the covariance matrix [Pillai, 1989]. The role of FBSS is to decompose the measurement array in sub-arrays of length L .

A single snapshot is defined by $y(k)$ where $k = 0, \dots, K - 1$ is the antenna position index in the virtual array. The FBSS produces the following measurement matrix:

$$\mathbf{Y}_{SS} = \begin{bmatrix} y(0) & y(1) & \dots & y(L-1) \\ y(1) & y(2) & \dots & y(L) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ y(K-L) & y(K-L+1) & \dots & y(K-1) \\ y^*(L-1) & y^*(L-2) & \dots & y^*(0) \\ y^*(L) & y^*(L-1) & \dots & y^*(1) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ y^*(K-1) & y^*(K-2) & \dots & y^*(K-L) \end{bmatrix}^T$$

The resulting covariance matrix is

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{Y}_{SS} \mathbf{Y}_{SS}^H$$

With this algorithm, we can produce a $L \times L$ covariance matrix with a rank of maximum L . This means that root-MUSIC can detect up to $L - 1$ targets.

In order to apply root-MUSIC, we must apply eigenvalue decomposition (EVD) on the covariance matrix and separate the noise subspace from the signal subspace. This means that we need to know the number of targets to find before detecting them. This can be achieved by using the AIC (Akaike Information Criterion) or MDL (Minimum Description Length) algorithms on the eigenvalue distribution. The processing chain is summarized on Figure 5.9.

With super resolution algorithms such as root-MUSIC, the resolution is defined by the probability to separate two close targets. This probability depends on the antenna array size, the angular distance between the targets as well as their SNR. This is different from conventional FFT-based beamforming approach where the resolution depends only on the array size and can be given by the Rayleigh criterion.

Figure 5.9: Angle of arrival estimation with root-MUSIC processing chain. \underline{y} : single snapshot capture. \mathbf{R} : covariance matrix. \mathbf{D} : Diagonal matrix with eigenvectors. \mathbf{U} : Matrix with the eigenvectors.

5.2.2. FMA modulation schemes

Frequency Modulated Arrays (FMAs) have been extensively studied in theory for their potential in beamforming and localization. However, practical implementations, particularly in silicon integrated circuits, remain limited.

Our previous work [Mannem,2022] successfully demonstrated an FMA-based IC capable of angular localization with joint communication capabilities, marking a significant step toward practical FMA applications. This implementation primarily addressed angle estimation, leaving depth sensing as an open challenge. Depth information is crucial for applications like 3D imaging and autonomous navigation, necessitating further advancements in FMA designs to capture range data effectively. To advance this field, we will explore joint FMA hardware and frequency modulation sequence designs to enable novel localization capabilities.

Figure 5.10: FMA system circuit schematic and modulation schemes.

As illustrated in Figure 5.10, the FMA (Frequency-Modulated Array) sensing mechanism operates in a time-interleaved manner between standard phased array and linear/nonlinear FMA modes. The standard phased array mode provides an angular and depth-agnostic scan, establishing a timing reference across the field of view. When the system switches to linear FMA mode, it introduces a time-varying beam scan across the entire field. As the beam sweeps past the localization target, a peak response is detected at the target receiver (RX). This peak's timing, relative to the reference set by the phased array scan, provides a time difference that is uniquely mapped to the target's angle of arrival.

A similar time-interleaving principle applies to the nonlinear FMA operation. Once the angular location is determined, the FMA applies known phase shifts to steer toward the target. In nonlinear mode, the system forms a highly localized 3D scanning beam in the depth direction. As with linear FMA, the depth information is encoded as a time difference relative to the reference signal, enabling precise depth localization based on time-of-arrival.

Assuming a 1 ns detectable time difference at the far-field RX node, which is readily achievable by standard multi-giga-sample-per-second ADCs used in advanced mm-Wave receivers, the system can achieve an angular resolution of approximately 0.2° and a depth (range) resolution of about 0.3 m using four antennas in the TX array. For a 10 ns detectable time difference, the angular and depth resolutions degrade to approximately

2° and 3 m, respectively. It should be emphasized that the FMA modulation speed at the TX array is different from the timing resolution at the RX node. For example, the linear FMA modulation in Figure 5.10 adopts a linear fixed frequency offset between adjacent TX elements as 2MHz [Mannem,2022]. In the far field, the receiver nodes are detecting the time-domain waveforms of the received signal, based on which TX-RX angular directions are detected. Therefore, the finer the far-field RX can time-resolve the received signals, the finer the TX-RX angular resolutions it can achieve. In [Mannem,2022], a 10ns timing resolution at the far-field RX node achieves 2° angular resolution in TX-RX localization over the full field-of-view (FoV).

5.3. Synchronization

A system overview of the blocks relevant for synchronization is shown in Figure 5.11. The DU/CU, which has access to fiber internet with SyncE, is assumed to be the golden reference in the system (it could actually also be an RU, as long as it fiber access but for the sake of unique non-confusing naming we will call it DU/CU). In order to support time stamping to UTC following the IEEE 1588 standard with Precision Time Protocol or something similar, reference packets will be sent by the DU/CU SyncE node. These are modulated in such a way that frequency and time information can be extracted. In the project 6G-REFERENCE, we design hardware for AP/RU nodes that can receive this frequency and time information and extract relevant PTP information from it providing time stamping to UTC. This time-stamping will largely be done in digital, but can be enhanced by hardware support, e.g. to improve time-stamping accuracy.

Figure 5.11 High-level block diagram of the frequency synchronization system.

5.3.1. Frequency and phase synchronization

To achieve phase synchronization for D-MIMO, the cooperating distributed RUs need to extract frequency and phase information from pilot tones as part of the reference packets

sent by the DU/CU, or if needed a continuous dedicated pilot-tone channel. Note that this goal of achieving phase-synchronous D-MIMO deals with relative phase synchronization, not absolute time. Translated to time-accuracy, it targets a much finer (ps) timescale which is orders of magnitude smaller than even the best achieved UTC-resolutions in cable/fiber systems (typically >1ns). Hence synchronization to UTC time is not critical for D-MIMO phase synchronization.

As shown in Figure 5.11, a reference extractor tries to extract frequency and phase information of the received signal. Assuming a simple channel model, the received signal can be modelled as an attenuated signal send by the DU/CU with access to the fiber, modelled here as an ideal clock with white noise added to represent the RF channel noise. This can also be modelled as a reference signal with phase noise. Assuming that half of the noise power is phase noise, while the other half is amplitude noise, we can calculate the phase noise introduced by this white channel noise as

$$\mathcal{L}(f) \approx \left(P_{rx} - 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{kT}{1mW} \right) - NF_{receiver} - 3 \right), \tag{5.1}$$

Figure 5.12 Approximation of phase noise of the received signal. For a received (narrowband) signal power of for example -100dBm , this yields a phase noise of -64dBc/Hz assuming a conservative noise figure of 10dB .

which is illustrated in Figure 5.5. This can be converted to TDEV, as used in $(\Delta T(\tau) = T_0 + \frac{\Delta f}{f} \tau + \frac{1}{2} D \tau^2 + T \sigma_x(\tau))$ (3.1), as described by [Rubiola, 2023] as

$$S_y(f) = \frac{S_\phi(f)}{v_0^2} = \frac{2\mathcal{L}(f)}{v_0^2}, \tag{5.2}$$

$$\text{TDEV} = T\sigma_x(\tau) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{8\pi^2} \frac{h_2}{\tau}}, \quad (5.3)$$

where h_2 is the white phase noise component of the fractional frequency fluctuation function $S_y(f)$. As only white noise is assumed, $h_2 = S_y(f)$.

Note that this calculated TDEV due to white noise in the RF channel reduces for longer values of τ , as averaging over longer intervals reduces white noise. In contrast, in section 3.4 we derived a *maximum* for the synchronization interval, to avoid that drift in the crystal becomes too high. This leads to a TDEV of the XO-PLL local oscillator within $\sim 1\text{ps}$ of around $500\mu\text{s}$. Combining with a minimum averaging time to achieve a TDEV of the received signal below 1ps yields a minimum P_{rx} of -113dBm , as shown in Figure 5.13. Figure 5.13, assuming a conservative noise figure of 10dB and a narrowband pilot tone signal. Note that the blue line shows the white noise averaging effect, while the red forbidden area shows cases where drift due to crystal drift becomes too high.

Figure 5.13 Required averaging time to achieve a TDEV of 1ps for different receiver powers. To keep the averaging time below the minimum synchronization interval of 0.5ms , a minimum P_{rx} of -113dBm is required.

5.3.2. Synchronization to UTC time

In order to achieve synchronization to UTC time, the propagation delay between APs needs to be corrected for. To do so, a PTP-like algorithm needs to be implemented. By assuming that the channel is reciprocal, the propagation delay and time error can be estimated by measuring the difference between transmit-time and arrival-time, assuming a sufficiently stable local clock is available (here the XO-PLL with high-frequency crystal-XO).

First the DU/CU with golden reference sends a message with transmit-time embedded to a neighbouring RU. The RU attaches a timestamp at arrival and calculates the time delta $\Delta T_{DU \rightarrow RU}$. Consequently, the RU transmits a message with the transmit-time attached and the DU/CU notes the time $\Delta T_{RU \rightarrow DU}$.

By exchanging these numbers, the propagation time can be determined by taking the average of the measured propagation delays. The time-error of the clock in the RU is the difference between the measured propagation delays. By knowing the time-error, the clock of the RU can be corrected.

Classically, the detection and correction of propagation delays is performed in software. Scheduling and queuing introduce nondeterministic delays adding additional uncertainty to synchronization packets. This can be mitigated by using hardware assisted timestamping, where the arrival of synchronization packets is timestamped by dedicated hardware blocks, removing these additional delays. In the White Rabbit project [Moreira, 2009], this hardware assisted timestamping in PTP is combined with Synchronous Ethernet (SyncE) to achieve sub-nanosecond timing distribution over ethernet.

If continuous phase synchronization is ensured for D-MIMO, correction for propagation delay needs theoretically to be performed only once when the RU is powered up. After this, the RUs stay synchronized relative to each other, and to SyncE via the DU/CU. There might be a drift of all nodes with respect to UTC, which can be corrected with infrequent time updates from the DU/CU to the RUs, taking negligible amount of resources.

5.3.3. Synchronization to PRS

Traditionally, time-synchronization is often based on cross-correlating a received signal with a known Pseudo Random Sequence (PRS). To enable coherent transmission from the different RUs of a cell-free system and D-MIMO applications such as distributed beamforming, accurate time synchronization between nodes is critical. The same holds true for providing positioning services, given that distances are inferred from time-of-arrival (ToA) or time-difference-of-arrival (TDoA) measurements and these can only be accurately determined if all nodes agree on a common time reference. As detailed before, this common time base will be disseminated over-the-air by a DU/RU synchronized via optic fibre to a golden reference. The challenge, therefore, lies in pinpointing precisely when a synchronization sequence is received so that the unknown times-of-flight (ToF), described in section 5.3.2, and denoted as $\Delta T_{DU \rightarrow RU}$ and $\Delta T_{RU \rightarrow DU}$, can be accurately estimated and accounted for when compensating the local clock offset. Traditionally, this is achieved via peak detection after cross-correlating the received signal with a known synchronization sequence. However, in the presence of noise, this simple technique does not guarantee a monotonically decreasing probability of a false alarm and missed

detection with increasing SNR – in fact, for different channel fading gains, one must dynamically adjust the correlation threshold to maintain performance. To work around this limitation, and as described in more detail in section 3.5, we propose to implement a “Transient Correlator”. Although this algorithm also exploits the cross-correlation of the received signal with a pseudo-random sequence (PRS), it does so while accounting for every possible shift within the time window of interest and offering robust performance in the face unknown and varying channel fading gains.

6. Self-interference cancellation techniques

Increasing the capacity of communication systems can be achieved by increasing the spectrum resources or by a more efficient use of them. In-band co-polarized full-duplex (just full duplex in the remainder of the document) transmissions belongs to this second alternative. It promises doubling system capacity by simultaneously transmitting and receiving in the same frequency band and same polarization. The main challenge is to reduce the so-called self-interference (SI), i.e. the leakage from the transmit ports to the receive ports within the same transceiver. Typically, SI cancellation is achieved with a multi-layer approach, deploying cancellation techniques at RF, IF, and baseband/digital levels. When a single antenna or just two antennas are used for full-duplex transmission, as considered in most full-duplex works, RF cancelling paths between Tx and Rx chains can be implemented to counteract SI. However, such schemes do not scale well with the increase of the number of antennas, since an RF cancelling path would be needed for each Tx-Rx port combination. Therefore, the use of larger antenna arrays for full duplex becomes a challenge and an opportunity at the same time. A challenge because RF cancelling techniques become unaffordable and an opportunity because transmit and receive beamforming can be used to reduce SI to proper levels. Note however that the latter is not free from challenges. SI reduction consumes beamforming degrees of freedom reducing the capabilities of forming far-field narrow beams and cancelling interferences to/from other transceivers. This will impact the link margin, but it can be still beneficial if the benefit in SI reduction is larger. Next sections discuss in detail SI cancellation techniques at the different layers: antenna / beamforming, RF and base band.

6.1. Self-interference cancellation through beamforming

In-band full-duplex (FD) techniques received a lot of research attention during the last decade, as they promise to double spectral efficiency [Sabharwal2014], reduce latency and allowed for more flexible scheduling of data streams. Most works in the field focusses

on sub-6-GHz carrier frequencies, as discussed in the recent very comprehensive overview in [Kolodziej2019] that describes and classifies 165 papers in the field. Despite this research effort, commercial success is still very limited as full duplex at low-GHz frequencies turns out to be extremely challenging. The resulting self-interference can easily saturate the Low-Noise Amplifier (LNA) and the rest of the receiver. It can also corrupt the receive signal due to front-end impairments like nonlinearities and phase noise. Clearly, large antenna isolation is required here, but this is very difficult to achieve in practice. Actually, at low-GHz frequencies omni-directional single antenna systems are highly desired for reasons of size and cost [Debaillie2014]. Hence, a lot of full duplex designs try to realize some isolation between the RX and TX path, while still using one antenna, e.g. by using circulators, electrical balance duplexers and other techniques reviewed in [Kolodziej2019] or in [Nagulu2024].

At higher frequencies there are more options. As antenna size is usually directly related to wavelength, it decreases with frequency so that the use of a separate TX- and RX-antenna and even antenna arrays is quite feasible or even a must for a healthy link budget. Physical separation, combined with other isolation measures should then allow for reduced self-interference (less Tx-Rx coupling). Besides this straightforward solution, here we are interested in preserving the compactness of the antenna arrays. Therefore, we consider no separation between Tx and Rx subarrays, and we exploit directionality of active arrays. In this sense, reference [Kolodziej2024] complements [Kolodziej2019] by providing a short survey on full-duplex array prototypes and architectures. It turns out that most of the works use very small arrays, which demonstrates the immaturity of the topic. The survey also presents the two main array configurations: 1) using different sub-apertures for Tx and Rx, often with significant spacing to improve Tx-Rx isolation.; 2) using Tx and Rx in each element, typically using different polarizations for isolation and enhancing isolation by integrated RF circuits like circulators or balanced duplexers. Note that this latter single antenna element approach does not address leakage between antenna elements in an array context. In all the cited works and in general in the literature there is minimum information about the specific beamforming techniques to handle the SI. Reference [Dastjerdi2018] explicitly states the use of optimization techniques, whereas in [Everett2016] a combination of closed-form expressions is used. In particular, on the transmit side, subspace reduction based on singular value decomposition is combined with traditional matched filtering or zero forcing. It clearly shows two inherent challenges of full-duplex beamforming: 1) reducing the interference power at the input of the receive LNA to avoid saturation and 2) the cancellation of SI at the output of the receive beamformer.

6.1.1. System model

The system of interest, as sketched in Figure 6.1 consists of L full duplex links established between N APs. For the sake of simplicity, we assume that each AP communicates to only one other AP, so L point to point full duplex links are realized. As introduced in section 3.1, each AP is equipped with an $8 \times 4 \times 2$ array split in two subarrays of $4 \times 4 \times 2$ ports, one acting as Tx and the other as Rx.

Figure 6.1 System model with L full duplex links between N APs.

The signal \mathbf{y}_k received at AP_k , whose intended transmitter is AP_i can be written as

$$\mathbf{y}_k = \mathbf{w}r_k \mathbf{H}ff_{ki} \mathbf{w}t_i + \sum_{n \neq k} \mathbf{w}r_k \mathbf{H}ff_{kn} \mathbf{w}t_n + \mathbf{w}r_k \mathbf{H}si_k \mathbf{w}t_k \quad (6.1)$$

where $\mathbf{y}_k = [\mathbf{y}_{kh}, \mathbf{y}_{kv}]^T$ being \mathbf{y}_{kh} and \mathbf{y}_{kv} the received signals in the horizontal and vertical polarizations, respectively; $\mathbf{w}r_k = [\mathbf{w}r_{kh}, \mathbf{w}r_{kv}]$ is the receive beamforming vector at AP_k ; $\mathbf{w}t_j = [\mathbf{w}t_{jh}, \mathbf{w}t_{jv}]^T$ is the transmit beamforming vector at AP_j ; $\mathbf{H}ff_{ij}$ is the far field wireless channel matrix between AP_i and AP_j ; and $\mathbf{H}si_k$ is the SI channel matrix AP_k . The two channel matrices can be decomposed as

$$\mathbf{H}ff_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}ff_{hh_{ij}} & \mathbf{H}ff_{hv_{ij}} \\ \mathbf{H}ff_{vh_{ij}} & \mathbf{H}ff_{vv_{ij}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6.2)$$

$$\mathbf{H}si_j = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}si_{hh_j} & \mathbf{H}si_{hv_j} \\ \mathbf{H}si_{vh_j} & \mathbf{H}si_{vv_j} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6.3)$$

The first term in the received signal expression corresponds to the desired signal, the second to the interference caused by the other transmitters in the scenario and the third to the SI. It is assumed that the two polarizations are independently used to transmit

different data streams, thus doubling link capacity (i.e. we overall target 2x2 capacity doubling combining full duplex and dual polarization without trading them off, which would happen when using polarization isolation in each antenna element)). Therefore, the signal-to-noise-plus-interference ratio (SINR) at the receivers at AP_k are then

$$SINR_{kh} = \frac{|w_{rk}Hff_{hhki}w_{t_{ih}}|^2}{\sum_{n \neq k} (|w_{rk}Hff_{hhkn}w_{t_{hn}}|^2 + |w_{rk}Hff_{hvkn}w_{t_{vn}}|^2) + |w_{rk}Hsi_{hhk}w_{t_{ki}}|^2 + |w_{rk}Hsi_{hvk}w_{t_{kv}}|^2 + \sigma_n^2} \quad (6.4)$$

$$SINR_{kv} = \frac{|w_{rk}Hff_{vvki}w_{t_{iv}}|^2}{\sum_{n \neq k} (|w_{rk}Hff_{vvkn}w_{t_{vn}}|^2 + |w_{rk}Hff_{vhkn}w_{t_{hn}}|^2) + |w_{rk}Hsi_{vvk}w_{t_{vh}}|^2 + |w_{rk}Hsi_{vhk}w_{t_{kv}}|^2 + \sigma_n^2} \quad (6.5)$$

To calculate the link rates, we resort to the following truncated Shannon formula

$$\begin{cases} SINR_{kh/v} \leq 0 \text{ dB} & R_{lh/v} = 0 \\ 0 \text{ dB} \leq SINR_{kh/v} \leq 30 \text{ dB} & R_{lh/v} = Bw \log_2(1 + SINR_{kh/v}) \\ SINR_{kh/v} > 30 \text{ dB} & R_{lh/v} = Bw \log_2(1 + 10^3) \end{cases} \quad (6.6)$$

Finally, the total system sum rate becomes

$$SR = \sum_l R_{lh} + R_{lv} \quad (6.7)$$

The problem we face here is how to design the transmit w_{t_n} and receive beamformers w_{r_n} for all AP to maximize this sum rate. Note however that, leaving aside the full duplex links, the system described corresponds to the so-called interference channel, in which multiple non-collaborating transmitters transmit to multiple non-collaborating receivers using the same time and frequency resources. In general, the capacity expression and the expression of beamformers capable of achieving the channel capacity for the interference channel still are an open research problem. Therefore, here we simplify our objective to the design of practical beamformers that permit approaching the performance of a similar theoretical system with no SI.

6.1.2. Single AP design in line-of-sight

The previous section 6.1.1 shows how complex the interference landscape becomes as the number of APs and links increases. To focus on the impact of the SI, we initially focus on a single full-duplex AP communicating with a remote AP with the same antenna model, but with perfect Tx-Rx antenna isolation. The distance between the two APs is set to 25m, and the relative angle between them is swept from -60° to 60° to account for the impact of beam scanning. The remote AP is considered to always point to the AP under test. The wireless channel is assumed to be pure line-of-sight and frequency flat. Figure 6.2 shows the simulation scenario.

Figure 6.2 Simplified single node scenario.

In this scenario, the SINR for the AP under test are simplified to

$$SINR_{uth} = \frac{|wr_h Hff_{hh}|^2 P}{|wr_h Hsi_{hh} wt_h|^2 + |wr_h Hsi_{hv} wt_v|^2 + \sigma_n^2} \quad (6.8)$$

$$SINR_{utv} = \frac{|wr_v Hff_{vv}|^2 P}{|wr_v Hsi_{vv} wt_v|^2 + |wr_v Hsi_{vh} wt_h|^2 + \sigma_n^2} \quad (6.9)$$

where P is the total transmit power. Similarly, the SNR (no SI is considered) at the remote node becomes $SNR_{rh} = |Hff_h wt_h|^2$ and $SNR_{rv} = |Hff_v wt_v|^2$.

The far field channel matrices Hff are just the steering vectors to the position of the remote AP, whereas the SI matrices Hsi are modelled using the S-parameters extracted from the electromagnetic simulation of the array.

For the beamformer design, we consider the following practical solutions:

1. Maximum ratio transmission and combining (MRT/MRC):

$$wr_h = Hff_h^H \quad wr_v = Hff_v^H \quad wt_h = Hff_h^H \quad wt_v = Hff_v^H \quad (6.10)$$

They maximize the SNR in both link directions but do not deal with the SI.

2. Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) in Tx and MRC in Rx

$$wr_h = Hff_h^H \quad wr_v = Hff_v^H \quad (6.11)$$

$$wt_h = (I + Hsi_{hh}^H wr_h^H wr_h Hsi_{hh} + Hsi_{vh}^H wr_v^H wr_v Hsi_{vh})^{-1} Hff_h^H \quad (6.12)$$

$$wt_v = (I + Hsi_{vv}^H wr_v^H wr_v Hsi_{vv} + Hsi_{hv}^H wr_h^H wr_h Hsi_{hv})^{-1} Hff_v^H \quad (6.13)$$

Performs transmit MMSE beamforming to cancel SI, assuming a receive beamforming based on MRC. It can be implemented iteratively, so after transmit beamformers are obtained assuming MRC in reception, receive beamformers are calculated using similar MMSE expression (since now transmit and receive ports are reversed). In the following iteration, transmit beamforming assumes the receive beamformers obtained in previous iteration. In practice, it is observed that the improvement over the first iteration is negligible.

3. MMSE in Rx and MRT in Tx

$$\mathbf{w}_t = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{f}\mathbf{f}_h^H \quad \mathbf{w}_v = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{f}\mathbf{f}_v^H \quad (6.14)$$

$$\mathbf{w}_r = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{f}\mathbf{f}_h^H (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{hh}\mathbf{w}_t\mathbf{w}_t^H\mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{hh}^H + \mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{hv}\mathbf{w}_v\mathbf{w}_v^H\mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{hv}^H)^{-1} \quad (6.15)$$

$$\mathbf{w}_r = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{f}\mathbf{f}_v^H (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{vv}\mathbf{w}_v\mathbf{w}_v^H\mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{vv}^H + \mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{vh}\mathbf{w}_h\mathbf{w}_h^H\mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{vh}^H)^{-1} \quad (6.16)$$

This cancels SI in Rx. As in the previous case, it can be implemented iteratively but no improvement was observed beyond the first iteration.

4. MMSE in Rx and MMSE in Tx for reduction of SI at RX inputs

$$\mathbf{w}_t = (\mathbf{I} + \alpha\mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{toth}^H\mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{toth})^{-1}\mathbf{H}\mathbf{f}\mathbf{f}_h^H \quad (6.17)$$

$$\mathbf{w}_v = (\mathbf{I} + \alpha\mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{totv}^H\mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{totv})^{-1}\mathbf{H}\mathbf{f}\mathbf{f}_v^H \quad (6.18)$$

with $\mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{toth} = [\mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{hh}^H, \mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{vh}^H]^H$.

$$\mathbf{w}_r = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{f}\mathbf{f}_h^H (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{hh}\mathbf{w}_t\mathbf{w}_t^H\mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{hh}^H + \mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{hv}\mathbf{w}_v\mathbf{w}_v^H\mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{hv}^H)^{-1} \quad (6.19)$$

$$\mathbf{w}_r = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{f}\mathbf{f}_v^H (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{vv}\mathbf{w}_v\mathbf{w}_v^H\mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{vv}^H + \mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{vh}\mathbf{w}_h\mathbf{w}_h^H\mathbf{H}\mathbf{s}i_{vh}^H)^{-1} \quad (6.20)$$

Here we follow the concept described in [Everett2016]. The Tx beamformer consumes some degrees of freedom reducing the power level at all Rx antenna inputs. Instead of using the subspace framework of [Everett2016], we resort to a MMSE formulation, in which all SI channels matrices are stacked in one, which is weighted by a scalar α that controls the level of SI reduction. Note that since there are more interference components (32) to be reduced than number of transmitting antennas (16), the system becomes overdetermined and the expression provides a MSE adjustment of the system. The main benefit of this scheme with respect to that in [Everett2016] is that it permits a finer control of the reduction level through the weight α . The solution in [Everett2016] may present rather big jumps when the number of used eigenvectors is reduced.

Since the power per port is limited, all transmit beamformers are normalized following $\mathbf{w}_t = \sqrt{\mathbf{P}_e}\mathbf{w}_t/\max(|\mathbf{w}_t|)$, whereas receive beamformers are normalized to present vector norm equal to 1 $\mathbf{w}_r = \mathbf{w}_r/\|\mathbf{w}_r\|$.

Table 6-1 summarizes the simulation parameters used and Figure 6.3-Figure 6.6 show the simulated SNR at the remote node (SNR_r), SINR at the node under test ($SINR_{ut}$) and the maximum SI power level at any of the receive antennas on the node under test ($SImax$)

Table 6-1: Other simulation parameters.

Simulation parameters	
Distance	25m
Power per port	5 dBm
NF	7 dB
Bandwidth	400MHz
Central Frequency	15 GHz
Array element gain	4dBi
Element pattern	$(\cos \theta)^2$

Figure 6.3 Simulated SNR/SINR (left) and maximum SI level at any Rx input (right) for MRT and MRC.

Figure 6.4 Simulated SNR/SINR (left) and maximum SI level at any Rx input (right) for MMSE in Tx and MRC.

Figure 6.5 Simulated SNR/SINR (left) and maximum SI level at any Rx input (right) for MRT and MMSE in Rx.

Figure 6.6 Simulated SNR/SINR (left) and maximum SI level at any Rx input (right) for MMSE in Tx (for reduction of SI at RX inputs) with $\alpha=1.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and MMSE in RX.

As expected, the combination of MRT and MRC provides poor SINR at the node under test since they do not cancel the SI. In contrast, the other three combinations efficiently cancel it out but at the expense of reducing the gain towards the remote node, which also has an impact on the resulting SNR and SINR. For the MMSE in Tx, the reduction is on the SNR at the remote node, whereas for the MMSE in Rx it occurs on the SINR experienced by the node under test. Interestingly, this is lower than the previous, showing that it is more efficient to apply the cancellation at the receiver. Indeed, SINR reduction for the MMSE in Rx is below 1 dB.

The simulation results also show the impact of the different scanning directions, especially in the case of the maximum SI level at the Rx inputs, which increases as the scanning angle increases. SI levels between -6 dBm and -20 dBm are observed for the three first beamformer combinations which do not directly address this issue. The last beamformer, allows reducing the maximum SI almost always below -20 dB, but it consumes more degrees of freedom on the transmit beamforming. As a result, the SNR

at the remote node present large reductions of more than 5 dB for large scanning angles. The SINR at the node under test also presents reduction but much moderate in this case.

6.1.3. Impact of estimation errors

In section 6.1.2, almost a perfect cancellation of the SI was achieved. In practice such cancellation will depend on how good self-interference channels are estimated. Here we repeat the analysis but adding random phase or magnitude errors in the estimation of both H_{ff} and H_{si} following a normal distribution with zero mean and increasing standard deviation σ . Figure 6.7 reveals that the SI cancellation is very sensitive to phase errors. For a standard deviation of the errors of 0.5° the SI cancellation is reduced by more than 100 dB, which translates to a SINR degradation from 45 dB to just 20 dB. In contrast, the small errors considered have a negligible impact on the SNR of the remote node, so the MRT beamformer is not really impacted. As shown in Figure 6.8 the reduction of SI at the Rx inputs is also robust to phase estimation errors, Moreover, that reduction allows keeping a larger cancellation in the presence of errors. Note that now, SINR of 20 dB are obtained for standard deviation of 1° instead for 0.5° .

Figure 6.7 Simulated SINR/SINR (left) and SI level at the output of the Rx beamformer (right) for MRT and MMSE in Rx and a scanning of 30° in presence of phase errors.

Figure 6.8 Simulated SNR/SINR (left) and maximum SI level at any Rx input (right) for MMSE in Tx (for reduction of SI at Rx inputs) with $\alpha=1.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and MMSE in RX, with a scanning of 30° in presence of phase errors.

Figure 6.9 analyses the impact of power errors in the channel matrices estimation. It shows that the SI cancellation is much robust to magnitude than to phase errors. Although the perfect cancellation is destroyed for small errors, the achieved SI cancellation remains good in the presence of larger ones.

Figure 6.9 Simulated SNR/SINR (left) and SI level at the output of the Rx beamformer (right) for MRT and MMSE in Rx and a scanning of 30° in presence of power errors.

6.1.4. Self-interference cancellation bandwidth

In this section we check the assumption made of frequency flat channel, by repeating the previous analysis computing the beamformers at the central frequency of 15 GHz, but considering the frequency variation in both far-field and SI channel matrices. Figure 6.10 depicts the simulated SNR/SINR and the SI power levels at the output of the Rx beamformer when the remote AP is at an angle of 30° and we use the MRT and MMSE in Rx. It reveals that SI channel is frequency selective making the SI cancellation bandwidth really narrow.

Figure 6.10 Simulated SNR/SINR (left) and maximum SI level at the output of the Rx beamformer (right) for MMSE in Rx and MRT in Tx for a scanning of 30°.

Figure 6.11 shows the simulated SNR/SINR and the maximum SI power level at the input of any Rx port when the remote AP is at an angle of 30° and we use the MMSE in Tx to reduce SI at the inputs of the Rx and MMSE in Rx. We observe again the narrow bandwidth of the SI cancellation in Rx. However, the SI reduction in transmission is much less sensitive to the frequency response of the SI channel, though it cannot be considered as a SI cancellation but just a moderate reduction. Although this opens the possibility to explore other beamformers in Rx trading off the cancellation level with the cancellation bandwidth, it is more straightforward to consider an OFDM transmission in which the beamforming weights for deep cancellation are calculated per subcarrier or group of subcarriers. OFDM is the basis of 5G NR and it can be assumed that this in-band transmissions between APs would use the same framework.

Let us remark that this analysis is totally coherent with the previous one. The sensitivity to phase errors implies a narrow bandwidth due to the variation with the frequency of the phase of the SI channel components.

Figure 6.11 Simulated SNR/SINR (left) and maximum SI level at any Rx input (right) for MMSE in Tx (for reduction of SI at RX inputs) with $\alpha=1.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and MMSE in RX for a scanning of 30°.

6.1.5. Outcomes

The analysis in this section showed that practical closed-form beamformers can be used to cancel SI, thus not requiring complex optimizations. In particular, MMSE expressions applied in transmission to reduce the SI levels at the LNA inputs ensuring that they can work in the linear region, and in reception for a direct cancellation of the incoming SI provided promising simulation results. The SI reduction at LNA inputs can be controlled by a beamformer parameter, but maximum SI levels of -20dBm can be achieved with an acceptable degradation of the transmit gain. Besides, an almost perfect SI cancellation at Rx is observed in theoretical conditions. However, in practice, the latter is strongly

affected by the estimation of the SI channel and the operating bandwidth. Indeed, the cancellation is only achievable in a very narrow bandwidth, which suggest the use of OFDM systems to apply per-subcarrier (or group of sub-carriers) beamforming weights to preserve large SI cancellations. Even in this case, the SI cancellation is sensitive to phase errors on the estimation of the interference channel. For phase errors with a standard deviation of 1° , the remaining SI level at the output of the Rx beamformer could be around -50 dBm, thus requiring extra cancellation at IF or BB.

6.2. Spatial SIC for radar

Figure 6.12 Spatial SIC main concept.

The main concept of spatial SIC for a radar application is illustrated in Figure 6.12. As we can see it works in 3 steps:

1. Extract the parameters of the self-interference signal for each Tx/Rx pair. This is achieved in TD-MIMO where each transmitter sends a known radar sequence one after the other. Each receiver will apply range processing algorithm to estimate the self-interference propagation path. In this scenario, we assume the entire propagation path from Tx to Rx can be characterized by a single complex number (i.e. narrowband assumption).
2. Compute the beamforming weights for each angle using an optimization algorithm (which will be described later).
3. Store the beamforming weights in a look-up table.

This is a beamforming-based technique where the goal is to create a null at the receiver antenna location.

While the system is working, instead of using the conventional beamforming method, for each angle to target, we will use the beamforming weights stored in the look-up table. In comparison with the conventional beamforming weights, a SNR loss will be observed but this is required to allow a strong attenuation of the self-interference signal.

The new beamforming weights are computed with the help of an optimization algorithms which tends to maximize the self-interference signal cancellation with a constraint on the maximum tolerated SNR loss.

For each angle θ , the new beamforming weights are:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{w}} \max_{\theta \in \Theta} |\mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{a}(\theta)| & \quad \text{Minimize peak sidelobes} \\ \text{s.t.} \quad |\mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{g}_{n,k}| & \leq \kappa \quad \text{Limit spillover power to } \kappa \\ \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{a}(\theta_l) & = M \quad \text{Maintain peak gain} \\ M - L_{\text{SNR}} |\mathbf{w}|^2 & \leq 0 \quad \text{Limit SNR loss to } L_{\text{SNR}} \end{aligned}$$

6.3. Hybrid EM-RF-BB SiC Strategy

In classical single antenna full duplex RF architecture, the Self Interference Cancellation can be applied at the RF, IF, analog Baseband or Digital Baseband. Isolation may also be improved at RF by exploitation couplers. The purpose of having multiple cancellation mechanism is to limit the power of the coupled SI signal to avoid compression, and possibly to enhance the cancellation bandwidth as well.

Figure 6.13 Full compact rx/tx antenna array.

When moving to antenna arrays, the number of coupling paths increases drastically, making RF cancellation more problematic. Figure 6.13 shows a case where the same patch is used for Tx and Rx, but clearly this gives very strong Tx-Rx coupling. Moreover, neighbouring antenna elements couple as discussed in chapter 3. If we still would like to use RF cancellation, the complexity may increase with n^2 , where n is the number of elements in the antenna array. Hence, we propose the two following schemes shown in

Figure 6.14 . In Figure 6.14a, the two antenna arrays are separated by some isolator or by some increased distance between the two arrays. In that situation, the isolation can be so high that baseband interference cancelling can be enough. One can even consider using separated antenna panels. The drawback is that time and frequency reference will be different for the Tx and the Rx part because of the distance. In in Figure 6.14b, the two antenna arrays are adjacent so that the same time and frequency reference signal can be exploited. However, the RF coupling is stronger, although not as much as in Figure 6.13.

Figure 6.14 (a) isolated antenna arrays and (b) adjacent antenna arrays

In terms of complexity, the comparison is mostly in favour of the first solution. However, the antenna array approach also brings additional degrees of freedom, as it is depicted in [Doane17]. In that paper, two adjacent single dimension antenna arrays with four elements each are considered. Each patch is driven by one transmitter and one receiver simultaneously as depicted in the following figure.

Figure 6.15 Simplified block diagram of a digital phased array from [Doan17]

The receiver is either connected to the antenna to implement the receive chain or connected to a coupler in order to implement some interference cancelling. In that scheme, all the interference cancelling is implemented in the digital domain. In that system, a separate optimisation is conducted for the near field (which generate the coupling mechanism) and for the far field (which generate the signal at the targeted receiver).

The performance improvement can be evaluated at two levels:

- At the individual receiver level: In that demonstrator the initial coupling level is – 21.3 dB (without any specific optimisation) and after optimisation, it improves to –49.4 dB. Given our 80SI-reduction target, this isolation is clearly not enough, but early SI-reduction in the receiver helps to prevent excessive intermodulation distortion (Rx-EVM),, and this offers the possibility to implement further SIC later in the receive chain.
- At the overall receive chain, the adaptive beamforming can bring an additional 6 dB attenuation of the overall coupling
- The major benefit comes from the digital cancellation, which gives an additional 50dB interference reduction.

The efficiency of the proposed approach is wideband since it covers 100MHz bandwidth at a carrier frequency of 2.4 GHz. The drawback of the proposed approach is an increase of the output power of one of the power amplifiers by 3dB. It can therefore limit the achievable generate power.

It appears that this new degree of freedom brings a significant advantage with respect to the reduction of the RF self-interference cancellation complexity. The drawback is that each transmitter should be associated to a receiver in order to cancel out the coupling in the digital domain. However, in the scope of 6G-REFERENCE project, this constraint can be turned into an advantage with respect to the overall functionalities. The particularity of the future access point is that they will be devoted to multiple communication scenarios, as depicted in the previous paragraphs: AP to AP, AP to UE, but also sensing scenarios like radar. In these different scenarios, the specifications are different in terms of data-rate, propagation channel and angular resolution. Consequently, it would be interesting to be able to adapt the transceiver to the communication specification. As depicted in, the following figure, this can be easily done thanks to the double functionality: transmit and receive capability at each element of the antenna array. In the first array 6 columns are used to transmit, enabling an emitted power, whereas in the second configuration eight columns are used to receiver, enabling a much better sensitivity for the receiver.

Figure 6.16 Example of reconfigurability of the array. [\(show more?\)](#)

Since the radar functionality is requesting a large number of patches to reach a good angular resolution, it turns out that the number of patches will be too high for the communication scenario. As a consequence, we propose a new scheme where a column can be dedicated to the improvement of the isolation between receiver and transmitter. Some active transmitter will be only dedicated to achieving some cancellation of interference at the electromagnetic level, thereby, drastically improving the isolation with respect to Doane's approach.

Figure 6.17: Full duplex antenna-array with improved isolation.

6.4. Mixed analog-digital baseband SIC

Figure 6.18: Baseband SIC concept.

The main concept of baseband SIC is illustrated in Figure 6.18. As we can see it works in 3 steps:

1. Extract the parameters of the self-interference signal
2. Compute, in digital domain, the cancellation signal to inject
3. Inject the cancellation signal, in analog domain, at the receiver mixer output on the I and Q branches

The way how the cancellation signal is computed is described more in detail on Figure 6.19. On a transceiver chip, we can assume that we know the transmitted digital signal $b(n)$. But the self-interference signal $y(t)$ is unknown as we do not know the self-interference signal propagation path $h(t)$. In this scenario, the self-interference signal is defined by:

$$y(t) = h(t) * b(t)$$

The role of the baseband SIC algorithm is to estimate $h(t)$. To do so, we assume that the DAC on the transmitter is a perfect zero-order DAC such that:

$$b(t) = \sum_n b(n) U(t - nT_c)$$

where

$$U(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 0 \leq t < T_c \\ 0 & \text{elsewhere} \end{cases}$$

This is, of course, not realistic because the DAC has a limited bandwidth. This is modelled by a low-pass filter ('Tx Filter' on Figure 6.19) and is part of the impulse response $h(t)$ which must be estimated.

The estimation of the impulse response $h(t)$ is done using the OFDM radar range processing algorithm. As we know that the propagation delay of the self-interference signal is negligible in comparison with the radar range resolution, we know that the impulse response $h(t)$ is in the first range bins of the estimated range profile. The number of range bins to consider is the number of taps of the filter $h(t)$ that we want to estimate. This is done via an iterative algorithm which aims at minimizing the mean square error (LMS update in Figure 6.19):

$$\tilde{h}_{k+1}(n) = \tilde{h}_k(n) - \mu \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} \frac{\partial |r(l)|^2}{\partial \tilde{h}(n)}$$

where μ is the update rate, k is the iteration index and L is the number of range bins (i.e. number of taps) to consider.

Ideally, the first range bins of the range profile should correspond to the discrete time impulse response $\tilde{h}(n)$ which is the estimate of $h(t)$. Unfortunately, between the mixer output and the ADC, we have low-pass filters which will also be observed in the range profile. In addition, the DAC used to generate the cancellation signal has a limited bandwidth which will degrade the signal before injection. This can also be model by a low-pass filter. All those effects must be taken into account. They correspond to the green block on Figure 6.19 and are called the secondary path.

This second path must be estimated prior to the estimation of $\tilde{h}(n)$. To do so, we can turn off the transmitters and inject a known signal on the I and Q branches through the DACs of the cancellation path. But computing the range profile, we get a discrete estimate $\tilde{q}(n)$ of the secondary path. This one will be used to compute $\tilde{h}(n)$ via the LMS update:

$$\tilde{h}_{k+1}(n) = \tilde{h}_k(n) - 2\mu \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} r(l+n)q(l)$$

This algorithm is also called x-LMS.

Figure 6.19: Baseband SIC algorithm.

It is important to note that this algorithm assumes that the self-interference signal propagation path can be approximated by an impulse response (i.e. linear propagation path). In radar, we can force this approximation to be correct by designing a waveform which has low PAPR such that the power amplifier can be assumed to be linear even at the 1dB compression point. In wireless communication, the signal has a much higher PAPR which means that a back-off is required to limit the compression due to power amplifier. Also, the IQ imbalance of the transmitter can degrade the signal. Therefore, a possible approach is to use the radar functionality of the chip to estimate $h(t)$ and to use that estimate for the baseband SIC during the communication part. To maximize the performance of the system, it is recommended that the same back-off is used in both cases. This will result in a SNR loss in radar but as, we saw previously, we have enough margin to tolerate some SNR loss.

6.5. Time domain SI Isolation with TMA

Traditional full duplex systems achieve antenna isolation by antenna design techniques. Such isolation can also be achieved in the time-domain, and this is what we propose to explore using Time Modulated Array techniques, earlier published in [Huang22] and [Huang23] and conceptually illustrated in Figure 6.20. The idea of such Time Modulated

Arrays is to modulate the operation of the array elements in the time domain with ON/OFF switching schemes to be able to concurrently communicate with multiple spatial directions at different IF frequencies. Consequently, by combining a Time Modulated RX Array with a Time Modulated TX Array, while time interleaving the operation of the two arrays, full duplex operation may be achieved with reduced SI. Combining the TMA TX array and RX array can be achieved either in a co-apertured antenna array (for major size reduction) or a non-co-apertured antenna array (to further utilize the antenna-domain TX-RX isolation). Note this TMA-based time-domain SI approach is completely different from the conventional time-domain duplexing (TDD) operations. This is because the TMA operations allow time-interleaving the TX array and RX array beyond the Nyquist rate of the communication or radar symbol rates, which combined with proper baseband filtering, will not affect and essentially appear transparent for the original communication/sensing modulation schemes or operations (such as OFDM in communication and FMCW in radar sensing). Moreover, compared to traditional full duplex schemes, the envisioned SI isolation using Time Modulated Array techniques may offer the advantages of: (1) achieving satisfactory SI isolation without restricting the antenna array configuration to specific geometries, and (2) less hardware implementations complexities with either SI cancellers free or at least with cancellers with much relaxed requirements.

Figure 6.20: Conceptual operation of Time Modulated Arrays

6.6. Summary of SIC techniques

We have discussed several Self-Interference Cancellation techniques, and it may not be easy to understand the differences between them. In an attempt to create some overview, we have added Table 6-2 below. It lists the name of the technique, its input and output, and the operation performed to realize SI. Coarsely speaking there are two types of operations:

- 1) Mimicking the transfer function of the SI-path
- 2) Applying a form of beamforming

As there are different points to tap the SI (e.g. digital, RF, antenna patches), while there are also different points to inject the correction signal, there are quite some different forms of SIC. In the last column we also mention the section in the report where this variant is discussed. Moreover, especially analog capabilities may be limited, asking for an approximation of the ideal transfer functions. Examples would be RF-SIC using a phase shift as approximation of a delay and RF Spatial Tx-SIC using an LO-phase shift as approximation of digital Tx-beamforming.

Table 6-2: Overview of different variants of Self-Interference Cancellation techniques.

SIC-technique	SI Input	Output	Operation (Report section)
Digital BB-SIC	Digital Tx	Digital Canceller	Multi-tap FIR filter (6.1)
RF-SIC	PA-out tap	LNA in or out	Amplitude, Phase (4.2)
Dig. Spatial Tx-SIC	Digital Tx	Tx-DAC	Tx-Beamforming (6.1)
RF Spatial Tx-SIC	Tx-LO	Tx mixer-LO	Tx-Beamforming (4.2)
Hybrid SIC	SI-Sense (SIS)	Rx-beamformer	Rx-Beamforming (6.3)
COM Spatial SIC	Rx OFDM out	Digital Canceller	Rx-beamforming (6.1)
Radar Spatial SIC	Digital Rx	Tx-beamformer	Tx-beamforming (6.2)
Mixed A/D BB-SIC	Digital Rx	Analog Canceller	Multi-tap FIR filter (6.4)

Another important distinction between SIC techniques may be their suitability for wideband operation. For direct coupling, SI only changes gradually with frequency, so that a simple amplitude and phase correction can be sufficient. To some extent this may also be true for near-field antenna coupling, but it certainly is not if the signal is radiated out, reflected by the EM-environment and then returns via multiple paths to the receiver antennas. In that latter case multi-path components can cancel each other and very frequency selective behaviour may occur with large delay involved. This complicates the required SI-correction. This can for instance be handled by multi-tap FIR cancellers. Potentially also OFDM carrier-based phase and amplitude corrections can help here and this will be explored further.

7. Conclusions

This section should conclude the work done and outline next steps.

7.1. COM feasibility?

Preliminary study shows that, in TDD, the RU-RU and RU-UE link can achieve sufficient SNR to support the required modulation scheme. In full-duplex, we will have limitations coming from the self-interference. By simulation with the proposed 8x4 array, we found a worst case SNDR of 35dB and summed power likely just good enough for -30dB EVM required for 256-QAM.

In summary, the 8x4 array seems large enough to support a full-duplex link budget. It will be challenging to achieve 80dB overall SIC, and it will likely be necessary to combine the limited Antenna Isolation with Spatial SIC, to achieve together e.g. 50dB and add another 30dB of Baseband SIC (using the digital Tx-signal directly for baseband cancellation after adding proper delay and/or amplitude/phase shifting in baseband).

7.2. SENS feasibility?

The proposed system can achieve the required range and Doppler resolution when OFDM waveform is used. It should also be noticed that, as the proposed system will switch from COM to SENS, the OFDM waveform used for sensing can be optimized to achieve low sidelobe level. Therefore, it is possible to detect the required 0 dBsm target at maximum range without increasing the requirement on IQ imbalance PA back-off.

Regarding the angular resolution, different techniques have been proposed. They can be grouped in two categories: MIMO radar and beam-scanning. They have different requirements on the chip design. The choice of the proposed technique will depend on the chip capabilities.

7.3. SYNC feasibility?

In order to achieve the frequency synchronization requirement, we need to correct for time drift due to crystal flicker frequency noise about once every 0.5ms to keep TDEV below 1psec. About 30 fractional bits will be needed in the fractional-N XO-PLL synthesizer to keep frequency error below target 1ppb.

Regarding the time synchronization, the proposed method outperforms the conventional correlation-based procedure for varying SNRs, showing an improved ROC in every scenario.

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